

**ANALYSIS AND DESIGN OF UNIVERSITY OF ABUJA MINI-INDOOR
RECREATION COMPLEX**

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**A DESIGN PROJECT SUBMITTED TO THE DEPARTMENT OF
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DECLARATION

I declare that the work in this research work entitled “ANALYSIS AND DESIGN OF UNIVERSITY OF ABUJA MINI-INDOOR RECREATION COMPLEX” has been carried out by me in the Department of Civil Engineering, Faculty of Engineering. The information derived from the literature has been duly acknowledged in the text and a list of reference provided. No part of this research work was presented for another degree or diploma at this or any other institution.

Name of Student	Signature	Date

CERTIFICATION

This research work entitled “ANALYSIS AND DESIGN OF UNIVERSITY OF ABUJA MINI-INDOOR RECREATION COMPLEX” by ADEOYE ONAOPEMIPO VICTOR meets the regulations governing the award of the B.Eng. Civil Engineering of the University of Abuja, Abuja, and is approved for its contribution to knowledge and literary presentation.

(Project Supervisor)	Signature	Date
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DEDICATION

I dedicate this work to God, the author of all wisdom.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

I thank Almighty God for His mercy and protection in making this research work see the light of day.

I commend the great effort of my supervisor, Engr. Oseni for his support, advice and objective criticism given through the course of this research.

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ABSTRACT

University of Abuja (UofA) deserves a new, modern recreation facility that will meet the needs for tranquility and enhance extra curriculum activities amongst the growing students and staff's population. UofA currently owns three athletic locations, the basketball field located at the faculty of law, the convocation field and the school field situated along main gate terrain. All these athletic locations are limited in functional measures, esthetic values and do not portray the global vision of the institution. As a result, the mini-indoor recreation complex project will serve as a center which will provide modern day athletic opportunities and relaxation resorts for individuals who seek leisure at the bid of incurring social and physical values. The quality and scope of the project is a critical aspect of consideration in meeting the daring recreational needs of the institution. Structural analysis was performed on the design of the recreation complex, and suitable materials were used in the design. Materials proposed to build the complex are environmentally friendly, safe, aesthetic and economical in design. The proposed site is situated at the terrain adjacent Faculty of Pharmaceutical Sciences block, University of Abuja, Main campus. Based on the soil test report carried out at the Faculty of Pharmaceutical sciences terrain by the works department of the university, the bearing capacity gotten was 180KN/m² at the depth of 1.2m. It was therefore assumed that at the depth of 1.2m, the foundation design for the proposed site would be based on the soil bearing capacity of 180KN/m². The structural analysis and design of the project was performed with the aid of a software, AutoCAD and ProtaStructure following the British standard for the design and construction of reinforced and prestressed concrete structures based on limit state design principles. The result gotten at the end of the analysis influenced the design decision and the specification for the design was given based on the BS requirement and agreement to economy and safety factor.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

DECLARATION	2
CERTIFICATION	3
DEDICATION	4
ACKNOWLEDGEMENT	5
ABSTRACT	6
CHAPTER ONE	10
1.1 INTRODUCTION	10
1.2 Background of the study	11
1.3 Aim and Objectives.....	13
1.3.1 Aim.....	13
1.3.2 Objectives.....	13
1.4 Scope of the study	14
1.5 Statement of the problem	15
1.6 Justification of the study	16
1.7 Limitation of study.....	17
CHAPTER TWO	19
LITERATURE REVIEW	19
2.1 CONCEPT OF RECREATION.....	19
2.1.1 History of Recreation Centres.....	21
2.1.2 Recreation Centres	22
2.1.3 Types of Recreational Participation.....	23
2.1.4 Benefits of Recreation.....	23
2.2 TYPES AND CLASSIFICATION OF RECREATION CENTRES.....	26
2.2.1 Trends in Recreation Centres.....	26
2.3 PARKS AND RECREATIONAL DEVELOPMENT IN NIGERIA.....	27
2.4 RECREATIONAL FACILITY DESIGN.....	28
2.4.1 Design and Layout	29
2.4.2 Zoning for Recreational Facilities	30

2.5 Zoning Recreation on Campus.....	30
CHAPTER THREE	38
MATERIALS & METHODOLOGY	38
3.1 DESIGN PLANNING	38
3.1.1 FACTORS CONSIDERED FOR THE ARCHICTECTURAL DRAWING.....	41
3.1.2 USE OF BUILDING SPACE.....	41
3.1.3 STRUCTURAL MATERIALS DETAILS.....	42
3.2 STRUCTURAL PLANNING.....	52
3.3 LOAD COMPUTATION	52
3.4 METHOD OF ANALYSIS & DESIGN.....	53
3.4.1 AUTOCAD	53
3.4.2 ProtaStructure.....	54
3.5 MEMBERS DESIGN	54
3.6 DESIGN PROCEDURE OBJECTIVES	55
CHAPTER FOUR	56
ANALYSIS, DESIGN & DISCUSSION	56
4.0 INTRODUCTION	56
4.1 ARCHITECTURAL PLANS.....	56
4.2 STRUCTURAL LAYOUT.....	59
4.2 STRUCTURAL MODEL.....	61
4.3 ANALYSIS OF STRUCTURE	62
4.3.1 Axial Load Comparison Report.....	62
4.4 DESIGN OF STRUCTURE	62
4.4.1 Slab Reinforcement Design	63
4.4.2 BEAM REINFORCEMENT DESIGN.....	64
4.4.3 COLUMN REINFORCEMENT DESIGN.....	65
4.4.4 PAD FOOTING DESIGN	66
4.5 DISCUSSION	67
CHAPTER FIVE	69

SUMMARY, CONCLUSION & RECOMMENDATION	69
5.0 SUMMARY	69
5.1 CONCLUSION	69
5.2 RECOMMENDATION	70
REFERENCES	72
APPENDIX	76

CHAPTER ONE

1.1 INTRODUCTION

University of Abuja (UofA) deserves a new, modern recreation facility that will meet the needs for tranquility and enhance extra curriculum activities amongst the growing students and staff's population. UofA currently owns three athletic locations, the basketball field located at the faculty of law, the convocation field and the school field situated along main gate terrain. All these athletic locations are limited in functional measures, esthetic values and do not portray the global vision of the institution. As a result, the mini-indoor recreation complex project will serve as a center which will provide modern day athletic opportunities and relaxation resorts for individuals who seek leisure at the bid of incurring social and physical values.

Between 2018 and 2021, there have been a significant increase in population on campus and commendable stability in the academic system which has on the other hand given rise to both demanding curricular and extracurricular activities. In order for the new recreation facility to be sustainable, it must be designed to handle current and future demands for social and physical development. The quality and scope of the project is a critical aspect of consideration in meeting the daring recreational needs of the institution.

Structural analysis will be performed on the design of the recreation complex, and suitable materials will be used in the design. Materials used to build the complex would be environmentally friendly, safe, aesthetic and economical in design [1].

The proposed site is situated at the terrain adjacent Faculty of Pharmaceutical Sciences block, University of Abuja, Main campus. Based on the soil test report carried out at the Faculty of Pharmaceutical sciences terrain by the works department

of the university, the bearing capacity gotten was 180KN/m^2 at the depth of 1.2m. It was therefore assumed that at the depth of 1.2m, the foundation design for the proposed site would be based on the soil bearing capacity of 180KN/m^2 .

The structural analysis of the project will be done manually and with the aid of a software, ProtaStructure following the British standard for the design and construction of reinforced and prestressed concrete structures based on limit state design principles [2]. Protastructure is an innovative structural BIM solution for structural engineers to model, and analyze and design buildings quickly and accurately [3]. The software will be used for the design of the concrete structure and roof steel structures with respect to the standard codes.

1.2 Background of the study

Traditionally, the term recreation has been thought of as a process that restores or recreates the individual. It is also has been seen as activities or experiences carried on within leisure, usually chosen voluntarily by the participant – either because of satisfaction, pleasure or creative enrichment derived, or because he perceives certain personal or social values to be gained from them. [4]

Recreation is the refreshment of one's entire being, mind and body. It is accomplished through any form of play, amusement or relaxation. It is a nonwork activity engaged in for pleasure in the form of games, sports, hobbies, reading walking and etc. Recreational activities are often culturally and socially structured, and within a culture, people tend to want to engage in similar modes of action. Activities defined as recreational provide easily identifiable situations that give immediate sanctions for people to relax. Games are one such structured device for defining a situation as a time to relax from normal work, seriousness or routine

responsibility. [5]

Recreational activities can be classified into two broad categories: passive and active. Passive recreational activities are those primarily intended to refresh the mind and therefore require little physical involvement. Examples of such are: walking, talking, reading, eating, watching, sightseeing and other similar acts. Active recreational activities, on the other hand, are those that refresh the body and therefore involve quick and brisk actions which require intensive bodily movement. Examples of such are field games, court games, skating, jogging, riding, boating and skiing. [5]

Both types of recreational activities are practiced by people of all ages, but for obvious reasons, passive recreation is more common among the old while active recreation is more prominent among the young. Apart from serving its basic function of refreshing the mind and body, recreation also induces competition and team spirit. It gives an opportunity to learn the important values developed through team spirit and cooperation and the sense of belonging to a group. Therefore, recreation provides social, cultural and educational benefits to the community, prompting social interaction and encouraging better human relations.

Recreation can produce economic and commercial benefits as well, both directly and indirectly. The direct economic benefits come from events and activities like spectator sports, stage shows and amusement parks. The indirect economic benefit of recreation is in the form of tourism. Many major recreational events and activities bring in people from far places. These people spend money in motels, restaurants and shops enhancing the local economy and thereby providing new jobs for its citizens. Another indirect economic benefit is the desirable quality that recreational facilities provide for a community, hence making it a more preferred area to work and live. Well-developed and adequate recreation and open space areas tend to

attract and hold people in the community through their positive impact on individual lifestyles. [5]

1.3 Aim and Objectives

1.3.1 Aim

The aim of this project is to design a befitting, esthetical, pleasing and portable edifice, which will serve the community of university of Abuja for the increasing need of social development for both students and staffs.

1.3.2 Objectives

- i. To design the architectural design for the mini recreation centre providing adequate facilities.
- ii. To analyse the concrete structural frame in accordance to concrete elements design codes. The codes include BS 8110-1:1997: Part 1: Code of practice for design and Construction, BS 8110-1:1997: Part 3: Design charts for singly reinforced beams, doubly reinforced beams and rectangular columns.
- iii. To analyse and design the structural roof elements in accordance to BS 5950 1:2000: Part 1: Code of practice for design—Rolled and welded sections.
- iv. To detail the structural concrete elements and steel roof elements in accordance to BS 8110-1:1997: Structural use of concrete, BS 5950 1:2000: Structural use of steelwork in building and BS-Code 6399: Part 1:1984 (Code of practice for dead and imposed loads).

1.4 Scope of the study

The design and analysis of the mini-indoor recreation complex would be of 1000 capacity with provision of basic facilities limited to;

1. Architectural scope:

- i. Multipurpose Court
- ii. Mini Mart
- iii. Electric room
- iv. Art room
- v. Spa room
- vi. Restaurant
- vii. Suya Spot
- viii. Cyber Centre
- ix. Store room
- x. Gymnasium hall
- xi. Officials' room
- xii. Game room
- xiii. Relaxation Joint
- xiv. Locker/Recess room
- xv. Reception spot
- xvi. Cinema hall
- xvii. Stair hall
- xviii. Restroom

- xix. Entrances
- xx. Sports seats
- xxi. Cinema Hall seats

2. Structural scope

- i. Concrete structural elements
- ii. Steel roof structural elements

3. Civil and external work scope

- i. External road
- ii. Elevated and ground tanks

1.5 Statement of the problem

As a result of the struggle of students' day in day out for survival, the rate at which students in University of Abuja are being engaged with tight and strenuous academic schedules gives little or no time for recreational activities. More so, the existing sport facilities do not measure up to meet the growing need for socio-cultural and physical development of the prestigious university UofA. To this end, it is a point of concern that the management of the university needs to put in place some organs to help in the growth of recreational activities on campus. The most suitable approach to put this in place is by establishing a recreation complex with certain activities that can attend to the recreational needs of the students without any impedance. This would go a long to reduce both mental and psychological stress for so many students and promote the socio-cultural, economical and physical values of the institution.

In expressing indigenous context in the design of recreation centre in UofA, case studies show that their compositions do not exhibit characteristics of indigenous context in

question and tourism with true local content. A building such as a recreation centre, can be a very important architectural statement; a statement which without spoken words can visually communicate the purpose of the facility, the design concept and architectural character. It is therefore important to have a basis of developing the proper architecture for a recreation centre for a particular culture. [4]

There are about three locations in UofA serving as recreational centres, but one must ask; Do they really serve the functions of a recreation Centre? Is the design appropriate for that particular culture given its traditions and history? How best can indigenous context be communicated through the architecture and structural engineering intervention? Does it really portray the global vision of the university?

Again, recreation as stated above is one of the basic requirements for mankind to live a balanced and healthy life style, this is because after the stress of the day's activities, one needs a place to relax and recreate. Hence, it became imperative that recreational centres be developed on campus. Providentially, the campus have arrays of open spaces for recreation for the university community which have not been organized even until the time of this study. Some of the open spaces have been overgrown with weeds while others which have not been overgrown by bush are being converted for other uses. The need to organize recreation centers in UofA is imperative to the health, aesthetics, economic growth and the general wellbeing of the students and staffs on campus. [6]

1.6 Justification of the study

Recreation serves as a medium of social association for man since he is a social being who has craving for collaboration with others in exchanging of ideas, thought sharing, express his emotions and to share information around a specific subject. To enhance such kind of

relationship the existence of a facility that welcomes every category of human cannot be over emphasized. This project will give one of such building. The project, a mini-indoor recreation complex will give an opportunity for people to interact with each other using recreation as a medium.

But amusement does have an aspect of good inasmuch as it is useful for human living. As man sometimes needs to give his body rest from labors, so also he sometimes needs to rest his soul from mental strain that ensues from his application to serious affairs. This is done by amusement. For this reason Aristotle says that, since there should be some relaxation for man from the anxieties and cares of human living and social intercourse by means of amusement-thus amusement has an aspect of useful good-it follows that in amusement there can

be a certain agreeable association of men with one another, so they may say and hear such things as are proper and in the proper way. [7]

1.7 Limitation of study

The project work requires sufficient time and since this is lacking, it serves as limitation to the research work. It was quite difficult to get access to the already tested soil bearing capacity for UofA due to the fact that the value varied from one location to another. With the time constraint, it was not possible to carry out a fresh test on the proposed site but rather an assumed value based on the soil test closest to the proposed site was used. This study does not cover the survey information of the proposed site and was designed based on assumed dimensions.

Changes in the functioning of sports and recreational facilities and changes in the population (society, people using these facilities) force this type of work to be repeated periodically. This indicates that those elements of the functioning facilities must be

maintained and improved at intervals in exponential proportionality to the increasing number of people using the facilities in the future.[8]

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 CONCEPT OF RECREATION

The word “recreation” according to Butler is heard today on every hand. Yet widely different meanings are attributed to it, and it is applied to a great variety of activities. Recreation is commonly referred to as a type of experience, as a specific form of activity, as an attitude, as an integral part of life, or as a field of work. He went further because of the diversity in use to say that recreation is usually considered as the antithesis of work. Singer [9] on his part used the two terminologies as one single entity. He described recreation thus: Recreational activities now called leisure time activities because they are done during an individual’s nonworking hours may consist of almost any activity known to humans”. Frost on his part sees recreation as that which one does when one is not required to work. It consists of the positive wholesome and re-creative things one does during leisure hours [9]

Miller [10] described leisure as: Leisure time is that segment of free time one devotes to the pursuit of certain goals inherent in the leisure process. Leisure, thus becomes a qualitative concept, a condition in which one has achieved these goals, be they release of tension, attainment of a sense of freedom, feelings of pleasure, joy, satisfaction of being creative and expressive of self [10]

Recreation can be defined as the refreshment of the mind and the body after work, especially by engaging in enjoyable activities, or can be understood as the activity a person takes part in for pleasure or relaxation rather than as work. By this token any material or object designed to achieve this relaxation end can be tagged a recreational facility [9].

Recreation could be defined in terms of formative and felt needs. In terms of normative need, it is defined as a set of philosophically necessary yet pleasurable activities undertaken during non-work time which restore and refreshes the individual and prepares

him/her for work again and otherwise contribute to his/her well-being. Considering felt needs, recreation could be defined as what an individual would do given minimum of constraints on high autonomy or it is a set of personally ideal activities in the mind of the individual which when given the opportunity he/she will undertake [10]. On sociological backgrounds, the primary reasons for engagement in a recreation activity is for pleasure and fun, though, involvement in the activity may have a serious commitment and self-discipline. However, when recreation activity is part of organized community or agency programs, it should be socially and morally acceptable.

For some, recreation means the network of public agencies that provide such facilities as parks, playgrounds, aquatic centers, sports fields and community centres in thousands of cities, towns, regions and park districts today. They may view these facilities as an outlet for the young and families enjoy recreation activities in community settings with means of achieving family togetherness or pursuing interesting hobbies or social activities. For others recreation may be found in a social centre or a golden age club, a sheltered workshop for people with mental retardation, or a treatment centre for physical rehabilitation [11].

Often, we tend to think of recreation primarily as participation in sports and games or in social activities and to ignore other forms of play. However, recreation includes an extremely broad range of leisure pursuits, including travel and tourism, cultural entertainment participation in arts, or hobbies, membership in social clubs or hobbies, membership in social clubs or interest groups, nature related activities such as camping or hunting and fishing, attendance at parties or other special events and fitness activities [12].

For others, travelling whether it be by trailer, motor coach, airplane, train or cruise ship, is the preferred mode of recreation [13]. Beyond its value as a form of sociability, recreation also provides major personal benefits in terms of meeting physical, emotional, philosophical and other health related needs of participant. The very games and sports, entertainment media, and group affiliations that people enjoy in their recreation time help

to shape the character and well-being of families, communities and the society at large [9]. Today, recreation constitutes a major force in our national and local economies and is responsible for millions of jobs, in such varied field as government, travel and tourism, popular entertainment and the arts, health and fitness programs, hobbies and participatory and spectator sports [9]. For a growing generation of young people, recreation and leisure have taken on a new meaning of adventure, risk, excitement and fulfillment as they seek to meld technology and recreation. The idea of recreation participation may not include any physical activity but focuses instead on internet games, downloading or sharing music, instant messaging and new ventures we have yet to understand. The activity may be as dissimilar as sitting in front of a computer screen to be involved in extreme activities such as skateboarding on a Bob Burnquist-designed and built 360-foot skateboard ramp with a 70-foot gap that must be negotiated to safely complete the experience [13].

2.1.1 History of Recreation Centres

Historically, recreation began with primitive cultures and was usually engaged in once the pressure for sustenance, security and basic needs are removed. This usually takes the forms of festivals, celebrations, feast, weddings and/or special mythological days [14].

Under the Greek civilization, the concept of recreation was given a different consideration due to the theories and practice of enlightenment by Plato and Aristotle. This influenced the growing height of professionalism in sports, public entertainment and competitions and the intelligent use of time as the purpose of life. This development saw the creation of recreation areas as Pedagogy, Gymnasium, stadium, Lyceum and Academy. However, with the development of agriculture, there was a class differentiation in societies which were divided into the ruling class and the other population, hence, recreation became associated with the high classed. Under the Romans, recreation was undertaken to maintain physical fitness and for war. It was utilitarian rather than aesthetic. This therefore enhanced the provision of Baths, amphitheaters and arenas for the benefit of the

population. These activities included music, drama and sports, subsequently it included contest, chariots race, land and sea battle. In Egyptians, Assyrian and Babylonia cultures, recreation was considered as activities of the nobility, military and religious leaders i.e. participation in royal estate and parks. During the industrial revolution of the eighteenth and nineteenth century, a great influx of population was experienced from villages to cities, this however, took place with attendant consequences experienced in rise of population, overcrowding, poor housing, poverty, increase in crime etc. this also meant the migrating population left rural areas where they lived amid nature and where it was possible to walk in countryside to live in cramped conditions with little room to play and where recreation was impossible due to working conditions. [10]

2.1.2 Recreation Centres

Recreation centres originated from different needs of the societies. A recreation centre is a place where activities undertaken at free hours and after-work take place. It is a place where a particular or different set of activities take place usually chosen at freewill and without compulsion [10].

The concept of recreation centres is as old as human civilization originating from Paleolithic periods through Neolithic periods through to the various established empires such as The Assyrian, Egyptian, Greek and Roman Empires. However, the phenomenon of recreation centers became more advanced for example in the 1800's, artificial lakes were created and the areas were provided with regularly moved grass pathways with carriages. Reform parks in the 1900-1930's, where parks were segregated by age and gender and centered on children character development. Recreational facilities, where it became an expectant part of urban life were driven by the concept of demand rather than the service ethic of moral consideration.

2.1.3 Types of Recreational Participation

Types of participation may depend on whether the activity is;

- i. Sports: In sports participation, it could be active participation which may include both sport and fitness or passive participation which includes spectator and video participation. Common sports that may easily be involved in are; Exercise Walking, Swimming, Exercising with equipment in a gym, Camping, Bicycle, riding, Bowling, Fishing – freshwater, Billiards, Basketball, Hiking.
- ii. Travel and Touring: This includes activities like Domestic travel, International travel, short trips, Travel for business.
- iii. Entertainment Complexes: They include Traditional amusement parks, Theme parks, Sport Stadiums.
- iv. Outdoor Recreation: This includes activities in the outdoors and with the outdoor environment. Outdoor settings may be in town, in a wilderness area, parks, campus and other outdoor areas.
- v. Cultural Activities: They include Cultural centers, Amphitheatres, open air theaters; Arts, Music, Dance.
- vi. TV and Technology as Popular Culture: Television in households, use of computer, Use of television and technology for entertainment.

2.1.4 Benefits of Recreation

While parks and recreation centers can have a measurable impact on state and local economies, they can have important non-economic benefits as well. In this report, benefits are considered advantageous changes. To curb these disturbing trends, healthcare and recreation professional realize they need to make physical link between recreation facilities and physical activity fun, safe and accessible by making opportunities more

readily available, actively promoting the link while a number of recreation activities involve physical activity.

The Physical and Health Benefits.

California's park, trails and historical sites are excellent inducements to physical activity. These varied recreational opportunities make physical activity interesting enjoyable, and encourage life-long fitness habits. The many documented health benefits of staying active include reduced obesity, a diminished risk of disease, an enhanced immune system and most importantly, increased life expectancy.

Reduces Obesity

Obesity continues to be a major health concern in the World over and is closely linked to physical inactivity. Overweight and /or obesity is associated with increased risk for disease, mortality and chronic medical conditions, such as coronary heart disease, hypertension, diabetes, gallbladder disease, respiratory disease, some cancers, and arthritis.

Diminishes Risk of Chronic Disease

Recreational activities also significantly reduce the risk of many serious diseases. The Physical Activity and Health: A Report of the Surgeon General in the US States that millions of Americans suffer from diseases that can be prevented or the symptoms improved through increased physical activity.

In 2003, the American Cancer society estimated that there were 52,200 deaths and 125,000 new cases of cancer in California. People who exercise have a lower incidence of colon cancer than their sedentary counterparts, according to 25 out of 33 publications on the relationship between physical activity and colon cancer [15].

Osteoporosis

Strong muscles, joints and bones can be maintained by physical activity that adds additional stress to strengthen the skeletal structure. Weight-bearing activity is essential for normal skeletal development during childhood and adolescence. Regular exercise, especially muscle strengthening, may protect against the rapid decline of bone mass in post-menopausal women and protect the elderly from fall and fractures by increasing their strength and balance. The benefits of physical activity on various types of arthritis are uncertain, although increased muscle strength, bone density, and connective tissue could provide some relief for arthritis symptoms. Participating regularly in other recreation activities such as hiking, weight lifting, and sports help maintain bone and joints health [16].

Many reports have shown that bone mass in physically active individuals is significantly higher than in their inactive counterparts. Sports that use one side of the body, such as tennis, best demonstrate how exercise can have positive effects on bone density [16].

Boosts Immune System

The physically fit person is less prone to illness. Studies have shown that physically active individuals have lower annual direct medical costs than inactive people. Active individuals had fewer hospital stays, fewer physician visits and used less medication. The savings were consistent for men, women and even smokers. If all adults achieved very modest levels of physical activity, the estimated nation-wide savings in America would be \$76.6 billion annually [17].

2.2 TYPES AND CLASSIFICATION OF RECREATION CENTRES

Four types of recreation centres have been identified. These are:

i. Commercial Recreation centres: these are profit driven and usually take place in health clubs and fitness centres. [4]

ii. Public Recreation centres: this is made up of programmes developed by nonprofit agencies to provide recreation facilities. This usually covers people of all ages and interest and may be in the form of sports or less physically challenging (nature walk) or arts and crafts. Such include YMCA in the USA. This kind of recreation takes place in the USA. [4]

iii. Corporate Recreation centres: this is usually for employees and paid for by companies, they could take place within the company property. For example, Lagos country club, ikoyi club, NNPC squash club, British American Tobacco club all in Nigeria. [4]

iv. Therapeutic Recreation centres: this includes programs developed by persons in the public sector and are usually targeted towards special population such as elderly, disabled or mentally handicapped. [4]

2.2.1 Trends in Recreation Centres

According to Schneidon and Clarkson, there are three broad based trends in recreational facility design. Although, and in some instances, there is an interplay of two or all of the trends playing the factors in the design. These include;

i. Nature based recreation centres: this take into consideration the existence of a natural feature that can enhance the tendencies of a particular or a number of recreation activities, these could be mountains, rivers, vegetation etc. example is the designing of recreation center to accommodate skiers, trailers etc. [16]

ii. Community based recreation centres; this involves the indication of the community interest in requiring a recreation center for specific or wide range of activities. This trend proves to cater for the immediate needs of the community and has the tendencies to accommodate wide participation. [16]

iii. Market based recreation centres; this trend involves a detailed market survey by developers, it identifies the market indices and the driving factors in recreation participation, analysis of possible recreation participants and frequencies and identifying a particular place with or without natural resources and developing it to meet market and patronage standards. This trend is mostly carried out by private developers and is usually economic based. [16]

2.3 PARKS AND RECREATIONAL DEVELOPMENT IN NIGERIA

To a developing nation like Nigeria, giving special importance to the advancement of recreational centres should not be viewed as excessive emphasis. It is evident that Nigeria is richly endowed with resources in abundance, be it natural, historical and cultural. [18]

The development of recreation in Nigeria could be traced as far back as time immemorial when the early man engaged in hunting, fishing, boating and traveling for pilgrimage either for pleasure or as a trade. Children were also engaged in playing (street fighting, catching thieves and running around) cultural dances, storytelling, lantern lectures and all other forms of enjoyment knowingly or unknowingly they were engaged in recreation. [18]

As time went on, the level of education and advancement in technology brought about awareness on recreation and also the demand for accommodation, transportation and catering services arose (Jegade, 1998) The development of recreational facilities and infrastructures are not only a prerequisite to successful tourism, but also an integral part of planning and development of tourist attractions.

2.4 RECREATIONAL FACILITY DESIGN

It has been identified that the concern for health and welfare of the community was the major influence in recreation planning and early planning policies appear to have been based on the philosophies of equitable distribution of facilities, expressed demands and social control [17]. Hence, recreational facilities should be designed to be functional and the buildings should accommodate a wide range of activities in order to meet the community's/neighborhood's needs. Buildings may range from the simple picnic shelter to complex community shopping buildings [17]. This is a task that cannot be carried out independently; it requires and interplays of some or all of the following: the involvement of legislation, government regulation, direction and guidance, public debate and consultation. Other identified indices include the geography of the area, land use, planning obligations and the need for facilities and amenities to fit within the community plans and cultural strategies [18].

However, recreational facilities should be designed with the following considerations for optimal success;

- i. Effective use of the entire area and utilization of the existing natural resources;
- ii. Inclusion of essential areas in the plan to ensure it fulfils the program objective
- iii. Allowing for participation by all classes of people within the community
- iv. Ease of access to facilitate ease of circulation within the facility;
- v. The design should have an accepted aesthetic quality [17].

2.4.1 Design and Layout

Recreation facilities are the last major step in a long chain of events leading to public enjoyment of basic resources. It is in this stage where environments are modified or created after many hours of research and planning aimed at solving the mysteries of man and his needs and the site and its capabilities. Design, like any other problem – solving process, requires that you know the problem before you can hope to solve it. It further states that the knowledge that is gathered at the initial conception of any project the better the solution is. The results of poor solution range from no use of the site to failure of the site. No use usually indicates lack of knowledge about the market-people while site failure is the result of lack of knowledge about the site [17].

Site failure has caused some rather strange reactions: a turning to cure-all plant materials that are both beautiful to behold and will withstand the trampling of thousands of visitors, and frantic poring over fertilizer lists to find something to strengthen vegetative growth. Although causes of site failure may range from too many people or too much use and this poses a lot of challenges to the designer, but the designer should as a result of study be able to know how many people the site should be able to stand such if one owns or operates a campground or recreational development of some kind, one should be able to know very well, how many people must stay, how many days one needs to break even. For public agencies and private developers, they have a right to know the extent of their investment and their expected returns whether it is worth undertaking [17]. A site has a built-in capacity to with-stand impacts. The limit can be exceeded by applying the full impact of a few visits or the reduced impact of many visits. Different designs produce different impacts. The carrying capacity of the site can be squandered or can be used wisely. Most of the impact problems we all have are due to poor utilization of the recreation resources and not thought of recreation as a product. Because it involves the psychological well-being of man and is closely tied to freedom of choice and esthetics, the economic aspect of it has been given most considerations at expense of the experience and interaction of

the market target. We have feared and rejected with righteous indignation the obviously evil intensions of anyone speaking of Economics [17]. The fact is, recreation is a product, a commodity that our society finds essential, one that a vast number of people pay for, one so important that it is government – subsidized but mostly rendered by individuals. It is against this background that significant progress depends on recognizing this hoping this will trigger the beginning to manage production of recreation as scientifically and as economically as other natural – resource based commodities [19].

2.4.2 Zoning for Recreational Facilities

Zoning in recreational facilities will require the careful organization of similar activities and will be based on the following:

- i. Active recreation: This requires different individual participation and may be in form of sports and other physical activities;
- ii. Passive recreation: This could be in form of participants’ watching or being spectators. This does not require rigorous physical activities but more of relaxation.

2.5 Zoning Recreation on Campus

The percentage of adults who engage in regular leisure time physical activity is decreasing, causing an increase in risk for several health issues. Research indicates that the more physically active individuals are in their leisure time as adolescents and young adults, the more likely they are to remain active throughout the lifespan. The number of individuals entering the college or university setting has continued to increase over the past decade. Institutions of higher education are supporting the construction and management of large recreational facilities on-campus for college students to use for

leisure time physical activity behaviors. Many administrators are aware of the benefits of participation in leisure time physical activity among college students including: higher grades, less stress, better adjustment and higher persistence to graduation. Given the increase in popularity of comprehensive campus recreation programs and facilities, there is a need for theory-based research to bridge the gap in assessing participation and developing intervention and educational materials to increase participation. [20]

Apart from increasing physical activity as one of the factors to combat obesity, physical activity has also been associated with a healthier self-image, lower stress levels [23], improved self-esteem [24] and maintenance of overall physical health [25]. There have been several studies that hypothesized that the determinants of physical activity participation are physiological, social, ecological and psychological [26]. Involvement in physical activity as one dimension of leisure has become an area of growing interest in recent years. Researchers have begun to recognise the importance of participation in sports and physical activity and, consequently, there has been an increase in the number of studies related to this area [27]. Specifically, participation in physical and outdoor leisure activities have been associated with lower levels of depressive symptoms, increased happiness and life satisfaction [24], and improved health and social functioning [15]. Furthermore, involvement in physical activities may promote an active lifestyle and associated health benefits [28]. The university is a critical context in which people consolidate a life-style that is likely to support their future health ([13]. The majority of the studies carried out on university students have observed that an active lifestyle is an important factor for mental health [14].

A large number of people currently attend colleges and universities, and their leisure time physical activity participation cannot continue to be ignored by researchers. Thus, research on this facet of physical recreation activity is important for leisure and recreation professionals to better understand participants' leisure behavior. If the interests of society are to be served, colleges and universities must recognise that all students should be

informed of the relationship between physical activity participation and quality of life, regardless of sex, age, marital or parental status. [15] emphasized that the development and operation of specialized facilities and services focusing on the on-campus recreational needs of students has become an accepted part of the administrative structure in higher education in America and worldwide. Moreover, knowledge gained from such behavioral research will eventually help practitioners as well as researchers. It is vital for leisure practitioners to know what motivates participants to engage in their services, programmers and activities, as well as to fulfill their needs and desires.

For leisure researchers, the development of a behavioral model or theory can help to organize knowledge and experience and stimulate and guide future research. It can also aid in the development of better explanations and theories. Leisure and Recreation Frameworks for Investigating Leisure Time Physical Activity Leisure has been defined using multiple definitions as can be seen in the literature. Most inquiries into the history of thinking about leisure begin with classical Greek philosophy, specifically Aristotle [21]. To sum up, leisure has been viewed historically in three ways: as experience, activity or time. Whereas, recreation is defined as voluntary, non-work activity that is organized for the attainment of personal and social benefits including restoration and social cohesion [22].

Over the past two decades, leisure research has generated a body of literature pertinent to understanding and increasing active living, including studies on time use, motivation for initiating and maintaining activity and influence of user fees and urban park use [21]. The evolution and importance of theory in leisure research have been recognized as essential to broaden understanding of leisure [8] Researchers studying leisure, parks and recreation have an important role to play in addressing active living and health issues [12]. It has become acceptable for leisure and recreation professionals to focus on the health outcomes and benefits of active living. Perspectives presented in the leisure and recreation literature have significant ties to the literature related to health behavior. Several of the theories and

frameworks presented in the leisure journals are similar to those in health behavior studies. However, one of the theories housed specifically in leisure studies is the Leisure Constraint Theory. One model of this theory was developed in 1987 by Crawford and Godbey, which centered on the construction of three models of leisure barriers: intrapersonal, interpersonal and structural [20] and is similarly structured to the Social Ecological Model. However, the Leisure Constraint Theory introduces the perspective of inhibiting participation or engagement. With its 'initial focus on the problematic' aspects of initiating leisure participation, leisure constraints research seeks to understand factors that impede leisure participation and otherwise compromise the realization of leisure-related goals [23].

According to Jackson, no constraint is experienced with equal intensity by everyone, although time and cost related constraints rank among the most widely and intensely experienced inhibitors of the achievement of leisure goals and a balanced lifestyle. The experience of constraints varies among individuals and groups: no sub-group of the Population is entirely free from constraints and each group is characterized not only by varying intensities of the experience of each type of constraint, but also by a unique combination of constraints. Thus, relatively less constrained by time, young people's leisure is typically affected by lack of partners, opportunities and costs. The transition to middle adulthood sees a decline in these types of constraints but a marked increase in time commitments. Although constraints inhibit leisure participation, they do not necessarily prevent it [30]. Instead, some people may negotiate through constraints and thus succeed in initiating or continuing leisure participation, albeit in a way that may differ from how they would participate if constraints were absent [13] In many instances, individuals are able to overcome or negotiate constraints in order to participate in leisure activities [30]. [20] found that college students used different methods of negotiation in order to participate in leisure activities and that the most common negotiation methods they used were time management strategies. Understanding the distribution of constraints in society,

how they affect people's lives and leisure and how people adapt to these constraints is a crucial task for leisure researchers [13]. College Students' Engagement in Leisure Time Physical Activity Evidence indicates that levels of leisure time physical activity decline from high school to college and activity patterns in college populations are generally insufficient to improve health and fitness [5]. The most rapid decline in leisure time physical activity occurs in late adolescence and early adulthood. Changes in leisure behavior are most likely to occur during periods of life transition, when individuals' roles, relationships and ecological contexts are altered [6]. Transition from high school to a college or university is a major life stressor for many students and is associated with an abundance of increased health risk factors including decreases in physical activity [1].

Healthy Campus 2010 identifies physical inactivity as 1 of the 6 priority health risk behaviors for college students [18]. The freedom to exert behavioral autonomy inherent in the college context and the self-determined nature of leisure combine to suggest that college students are faced with a great deal of choice in how they spend their free time [7]. Although college students have specific time constraints related to their academic schedules, they also have considerable discretionary time. The choices made about how to spend this time influence one's levels of leisure time physical activity, and various factors influence these choices. [19] found that 84.7% of their research participants (n =367) who were physically active as college students were engaging in physical activity at similar or greater levels six years after graduation [31]. Evidence indicates that physical activity patterns established in childhood, adolescence and young adulthood can determine quality of life in one's later years [31]. An emphasis on leisure may be crucial in helping people learn to enjoy physical movement from the time they are children into adulthood [21]. College students are exposed to many opportunities of socialization and behavior-governing norms, thus post-secondary institutions provide a unique environment in which physical activity promotion efforts can be delivered to a large number of young adults in an effective way [31]. In addition to research suggesting a decline in leisure time

physical activity during the transition to college, a greater proportion of Americans are making this transition, thus furthering the need to better understand and improve physical activity behaviors of college students. During the past three decades, the number of individuals with four or more years of higher education has nearly doubled. According to the United States Census Bureau [11], enrollment in two- and four-year colleges and universities in the U.S. reached 20.5 million in 2016, up 3 million since 2000. These increases in the college population provide the opportunity to positively impact leisure time physical activity patterns of this demographic. Campus Recreation One significant area of recreation is the growing field of student campus recreation [32]. Comprehensive campus recreation programs include formal and informal recreational opportunities such as intramural sports, fitness programs, sport clubs, outdoor recreation, aquatics programs and aerobic dance classes [32]. Campus recreation centers exist for reasons that align with overall missions of universities; namely education, enhancing the quality of student life and preparing people for the future. Over the past two and a half decades, colleges and universities have made major financial investments in recreation facilities that enrich campus life and enhance the well-being of their students.

One of the reasons for campus recreation programs is the positive impact that the use of such programs, services and facilities has on the quality of life of its users, most often students [10]. Campus recreation has important responsibilities in terms of promoting the overall well-being of students, helping to reduce negative or destructive forms of play, extending and enriching academic learning and contributing to other college and university goals [20]. The integration of recreation services with the overall student experience has led to an increase in importance of recreation programming on college campuses [30]. The physical and mental health benefits of engaging in the types of physical activity offered by campus recreation facilities are well known and strongly supported by over a half century of research. Research in the past few decades has shown that participation in campus recreational programs helps with students' wellness [10],

retention and recruitment [32] and students' overall satisfaction with their college experience [19]. Research supports recreational sport facilities and programs as recruiting enhancements, which increase overall satisfaction with the collegiate experience and make a positive contribution to institutions' retention efforts. A number of recent studies have focused on usage of campus recreation facilities as it relates to student learning, development and academic success [5]. Given the importance of physical activity for health, the irregular pattern of college students' activity and the potential for colleges to have an effect on physical activity, including free or low-cost fitness facilities, recreation programs and exercise classes, scientific study of this behavior is warranted [23]. [27] reported findings on the frequency of participation in campus recreation services in relation to health and quality of life variables. They found significantly positive effects of frequency of participation on four variables; satisfaction with life as a whole, satisfaction with experience at the university at which they were studying, extent to which emotional health interfered with social functioning and how often the individuals felt like they had "a lot of energy" [21]. Another study of college freshman found that students who used the student recreation center not only persisted at a greater rate than those who did not, but also earned higher grade point averages and more credit hours at the end of their freshman year than non-users [30].

Although there were a large number of students currently attending colleges and universities, their leisure physical activity participation cannot continue to be virtually ignored by researchers. Research into this facet of physical recreation activity is important for leisure and recreation professionals in order to better understand participants' leisure behaviour. If the interests of society are to be served, colleges and universities must help students recognize the implications of physical activity participation and its relationship to the quality of their lives regardless of their sex, age, marital, or parental status [15]. [19] suggest that, by emphasizing the on-campus recreational needs of students, the development and operation of specialized facilities and services has become an accepted

part of the administrative structure in higher education in America and around the world. Moreover, knowledge gained from this kind of behavioral research will eventually assist practitioners in their work. It is vital that leisure practitioners know what motivates participants to engage in their services, programmers, and activities. This information is also vital for identifying participants' needs and wants. For leisure researchers, the development of a behavioral model or theory can help to organize knowledge and experience, as well as stimulate and guide future research. It also can help in the development of better future explanations and theories [24].

CHAPTER THREE

MATERIALS & METHODOLOGY

3.1 DESIGN PLANNING

Design involves a lot of strategy and planning. From the beginning, clients, architects, and construction management must work together to find a cohesive project that fits everyone's standards. While it may seem like a given to put thought behind the planning process, the role of art of design planning to any given project cannot be overemphasized. [25]

Architectural master planning is the critical first step in any design process. It is the creation of a framework in which the whole project proceeds. Headed by a lead architect, a project's planning phase considers the entire picture through detailed work. The process involves examining the design and style of the building, surrounding infrastructure, local government requirements, and so on. It should also include determining the purpose of the structure, goals of the project, and other essential elements. By creating a master plan, the entire project is likely to go as planned and lead to an exciting development. With progress to the schematic design, the building concept is transformed to scale floor plans and building elevations for initial review and approval. [26]

The primary purpose of an architectural master plan is narrowing down the style and aesthetic of the project. Since master planning involves developing a framework for the entire structure, it also defines every last detail. Typically, architects work with their team outlining the design scope of the project. During the process, the team takes into account all aspects of the project, including budgetary, structural requirements, shapes, views, and other design options. [26]

Depending on the project, the master plan involves design information for uses, heights, setbacks. All in all, defining these aspects of the plan helps eliminate design options and narrow the focus. [26]

This process is followed by the structural design planning. The primary objective of structural analysis and design is to produce a structure capable of resisting all applied loads without failure during its intended life. If improperly designed, elements of a structure would fail causing serious consequences such as large expenses or ultimately losses in lives which cannot be compared with any cost. [26]

Once the architectural engineer sets the function and layout of the structure, the role of the structural engineer begins which can be summarized in the following steps to develop a safe, functional and economic structures:

i. **CONCEPTUAL DESIGN**

In this stage, initial design of the building elements (e.g. slabs, beams, columns etc.) is performed based on BS-code requirements.

It starts with general arrangement, selecting the appropriate columns' locations and orientation in such a way that they do not interfere with the architectural drawings. For example, columns shouldn't be in the middle of a room with moderate span. Also, one should consider that at least 30% of the total number of columns to be in either x- or y- directions to give adequate earthquake resistance of the building.

After that, the type of structural system is selected. For instance, the slab might be chosen to be solid slab, hollow block or flat slab etc. Accordingly, the location of beams is as well determined.

ii. **DETERMINING THE INTERNAL FORCES OF EACH ELEMENT**

After finishing the initial design, the exact dimensions of each building element shall be determined. First, an analysis model is created for the building with its initial dimensions as determined from (i) on an analysis software such as ProtaStructure.

All the loads that act on the structure have to be defined in the model such as dead loads, live loads, wind loads etc.

From the model, the internal forces [Normal Force, Shear Force, Bending Moments] on each element is calculated.

iii. **ITERATIVE DESIGN**

When the straining actions on the elements based on the initial sizing has been determined, they are then used to design according to the relevant code. The design process became so easy by using some spreadsheets or any other software that facilitates the design (Protastructure).

Next, the analysis model should be modified to the new dimensions obtained from the previous design and the analysis is re-run. Internal forces are obtained and design is made again based on the new forces.

This iterative process is repeated until the element design be the same in two following iterations.

iv. **FOUNDATION DESIGN**

After the final dimensions of members are found, the foundation system type can be selected taking in consideration, the bearing capacity of the soil and the loading coming from the structure.

v. **DRAFTING**

In this step, the structural plans are created. These plans should be fully detailed such that the construction process in the site can proceed smoothly and not delayed due to missing data in the drawings. [26]

3.1.1 FACTORS CONSIDERED FOR THE ARCHITECTURAL DRAWING

In the bid to achieve a sustainable architectural structure, the following factors were put into consideration:

- i. the relationship of the design to the location and the building purpose
- ii. the contemporary and original appearance of the design
- iii. easy usability and structure effectiveness
- iv. durability of construction and materials
- v. suitability and ageing characteristics of the materials used
- vi. flexibility for changes of use
- vii. possibility of conversion if required. [27]

3.1.2 USE OF BUILDING SPACE

The proposed recreation facility will offer features as indicated in the table below:

S/N	Program Area	Quantity
1	Multipurpose court	1
2	Mini Mart	1
3	Electric room	1
4	Art room	1
5	Spa Room	1

6	Restaurant	1
7	Suya Spot	1
8	Cyber Centre	1
9	Store room	1
10	Gymnasium hall	1
11	Official room	2
12	Game room	1
13	Relaxation Joint	1
14	Locker/recess room	2
15	Reception spot	3
16	Cinema Hall	2
17	Stair hall	2
18	Rest room	4
19	Entrance	3
20	Sport seats	710
21	Cinema Hall seats	190

3.1.3 STRUCTURAL MATERIALS DETAILS

The material selection was based on safety and economical satisfaction:

1. For Construction (Foundation – building height)

a. Concrete:

- i. Concrete mixing – 1:2:4
- ii. Concrete grade – 25N/mm²
- iii. Constituent for all structural elements (footing, columns, slabs, beams)

b. Reinforcement Steel

- i. Steel grade – 410N/mm²
- ii. Classes of steel; Mild steel round bar, R and High Yield steel bar, Y
- iii. Constituent for all structural elements (footing, columns, slabs, beams)

2. For Roof structure (STEEL)

- i. Side lap Corrugated sheeting

Figure 3.1 Side Lap Corrugated Sheetting

- ii. 75mm x 50mm Steel Purlins @ 900mm c/c
- iii. Long Span Aluminum Roofing Sheet
- iv. 100mm x 50mm Steel Struts
- v. 150mm x 50mm Steel Kingpost
- vi. 150mm x 50mm Steel Rafter @ 1200mm c/c
- vii. 100mm x 50mm Steel Wallplate
- viii. 150mm x 50mm Steel Tie-beam
- ix. 100mm x 50mm Steel Bracing

- x. 8mm Dia G.I Hook Bolt
- xi. G.I. Nut
- xii. G.I. Flat Washer
- xiii. Bitumen washer

Figure 3.2 Steel roof truss section

Figure 3.3 Purlins sections

3. WINDOWS

i. Compliance Standards

The windows and doors and the installation shall comply with all current British Standards, Codes of Practice, Statutory Requirements and Building Regulations relevant to their performance:

- a. The window assemblies are to be manufactured and installed to the highest quality levels and the manufacturer/supplier must produce certified evidence that they comply with the following summarised standards:
 - i. The BPWG/GGF Trade Standards for UPVC Windows.
 - ii. BS EN ISO 9001 and BS 9002 Schemes for: Quality Assurance Standards Management.
 - iii. BS 5368:Parts 1 to 3 and BS 6375:Part 1 – Classification of Weather tightness Operation and Strength Characteristics.
- b. Windows must meet the following ratings in respect of Exposure Category B:
 - i. Air permeability - 600 PA
 - ii. Water tightness - 300 PA
 - iii. Wind resistance - 2000 PA

ii. Window Types

1. Side and Top Hung Casements:

The side hung casements and top hung vents shall be fitted using 2 No stainless steel projection hinges (friction stays) that allow cleaning when fully open. The locking mechanisms shall be multi-point espagnolette type. The gearing must enable the locking handle to be fitted in the lower third part of the sash and must engage into jambs, heads and cills/transoms and be coated with an anti-corrosion coating to BS 1706. The locking handle fitted to be white and provided with 2 No

keys. A night vent facility shall be incorporated on both opening sashes types. All opening sashes shall conform to the requirements of BS 7590 (formerly PAS 011).

2. Tilt and Turn

- a. The tilt and turn sashes must conform with BS 7950 in every aspect. The gearing shall be tilt before turn with night vent facility incorporated.
- b. The gearing for the “tilt” and “turn” modes must not be capable of being operated simultaneously such that the opening light is pivoted on one hinge. Windows shall therefore be fitted with a switch barrier to prevent this occurring.

3. Vertical Sliding Windows

To have locking cam tilt catches with shoot bolts and be capable of dropping inwards for cleaning. Tilt restrictors both sides, limit stops, pole eye top sash and 2 No. handles to both top and bottom sashes. Caldwell Torso pre-tension balance with shackles fitted to either side of both sashes (heavy duty), pivot shoes to bottom of spring balances. A night vent facility is to be incorporated.

4. Top Hung Windows

To have Multi-Point Shoot bolt locking arrangements which conform to BS 7950 (PAS011). The operating handle shall be lockable. A night vent facility must be incorporated.

iii. Sundries

a. Window Cills

New windows and doors are to be provided with cills of sizes appropriate to maintain the projection of existing cills beyond the face of external walls.

b. Safety Devices

All windows are to be fitted with a safety restrictor device which will restrict the opening to not less than 90mm and not more than 100mm.

iv. Safety Devices and Limiting Stays

- a. Are to be pre-finished with an anti-corrosion coating and shall be self-engaging and restrict the opening, but be secure.
- b. The position of Safety Devices and Limiting Stays are not to exceed those recommended in BS 8213: Part 1, and must be securely fixed.

v. Fastening and Fixings

All screws, nuts, bolts, rivets and other fastening shall be of corrosion resistant material, stainless steel 300 series or other equal and approved. Where surface fixed and generally seen, screws, etc. to be colored white to match frame.

4. Doors

- a. Note: This section excludes front entrance doors.
- b. Each door to be capable of being operated and locked from both inside and outside with the exception of emergency escape doors which must only be locked on the inside with a thumb turn.
- c. Each door is to be hung on a minimum of three heavy duty hinges with zinc die cast bodies, white polyester powder coating, nylon bushes and stainless-steel security pin. External projecting hinges shall not be used unless with prior approval in

which case they must be a type where it is not possible to “punch out” the hinge pin i.e. a security screw to prevent removal of centre pin should be included. Outward opening doors are to have concealed restrictors to limit the opening to 90°. Inward opening doors to have a door stop.

- d. Handles are to be satin anodised aluminium lever handles internally and externally with satin anodised aluminium back plates.
- e. Doors to have multi point locking espagnolette bolt system operated by a six-lever cylinder lock to BS 7950. The doors must conform to PAS 24. [28]

5. Finishes

Finishes are used in the final part of the construction or manufacturing process, forming the final surface of an element. They can protect the element they finish from impact, water, frost, corrosion, abrasion, and so on, and/or they can be decorative.

Finishes commonly relate to internal surfaces, but they may also be applied to external elements. They can be applied wet or dry. Some elements are self-finished, that is the final surface is part of the material the element is formed from.

The application of finishes may involve the build up of more than one layer, which, whilst some of the layers will form the final exposed surface, they are nonetheless considered to be finishes. For example, an undercoat or primer might be applied to a wall before the final paint.

NBS categorise finishes as:

- a. Calcium sulfate based levelling screeds.
- b. Cement based levelling / wearing screeds.
- c. Decorative papers / fabrics.
- d. Edge fixed carpeting.
- e. Insulation with rendered finish.

- | | |
|--|---|
| f. Intumescent coatings for fire protection of steelwork. | l. Rubber / plastics / cork/ lino / carpet tiling / sheeting. |
| g. Mastic asphalt flooring/ floor underlays. | m. Sprayed monolithic coatings. |
| h. Metal lathing / anchored mesh reinforcement for plastered/ rendered coatings. | n. Stone / concrete / quarry / ceramic tiling / mosaic. |
| i. Painting / clear finishing. | o. Terrazzo tiling / in situ terrazzo. |
| j. Plastered / rendered / roughcast coatings. | p. Wood block / composition block / mosaic parquet flooring. |
| k. Resin flooring. | |

However, there is some overlap in this categorization with other building components, and some classifications might place some of these items within other categories. For example, plaster might be considered a lining rather than a finish stone might be considered part of the wall or floor construction, and so on.

Uniclass lists the following choice of ‘decorative’ coatings:

- | | |
|-------------------------------|--|
| i. Aluminium paints. | x. High pigment water-borne paint. |
| ii. Casein paints. | |
| iii. Cement paints. | xi. Limewashes. |
| iv. Concrete finishing coats. | xii. Micaceous iron oxide paints. |
| v. Concrete flash coats. | xiii. Multi-colour coatings. |
| vi. Concrete floor dyes. | xiv. Multi-colour finish spatter coatings. |
| vii. Concrete floor paints. | |
| viii. Concrete stains. | xv. Oil-bound distempers. |
| ix. Distemper. | xvi. Plant oil paints. |

- xvii. Plastic texture paints.
- xviii. Resin-based breathable masonry paints.
- xix. Semi-transparent timber stains and dyes.
- xx. Silicate-based masonry coatings.
- xxi. Solvent-based finishing coats.
- xxii. Solvent-borne gloss finishes.
- xxiii. Solvent-borne masonry paints.
- xxiv. Solvent-borne matt and flat finishes.
- xxv. Solvent-borne mid-sheen finishes.
- xxvi. Tallow lime washes.
- xxvii. Water-borne gloss finishes.
- xxviii. Water-borne masonry paints.
- xxix. Water-borne matt and flat finishes.
- xxx. Water-borne mid-sheen finishes.

The choice of finishes might be influenced by factors, such as:

- i. Colour and appearance (matt, gloss, silk, and so on).
- ii. Texture.
- iii. Maintenance and cleaning requirements.
- iv. Durability.
- v. Expected life.
- vi. Weather resistance.
- vii. Corrosion resistance.
- viii. Availability.
- ix. Preparation required.
- x. Ease of application.
- xi. Drying time.
- xii. Cost.
- xiii. Safety or environmental issues.
- xiv. Waste. [29]

3.2 STRUCTURAL PLANNING

The structural layouts are formed by assemblage of the general arrangement identifying the different structural elements such as the beams, slabs, columns, footing. The proposed building was treated as a framed building structure.

3.3 LOAD COMPUTATION

The loading system is based on the BS-Code 6399: Part 1:1984 (Code of practice for dead and imposed loads)

3.4 METHOD OF ANALYSIS & DESIGN

The analysis was done for RCC framed structure to determine the Shear Forces, Bending Moment and deflections. This was done with the aid of software stated below:

- i. AutoCAD – For drafting architectural plans and structural layouts
- ii. ProtaStructure- For analysis and design of the structure.

3.4.1 AUTOCAD

AutoCAD is, certainly, the most recognized software for architecture and engineering by far. Infact, it is almost impossible to achieve any engineering design process without starting from AUTOCAD. Thus, the grass-root for communication in design process.

AutoCAD is a software program which has been used in many industries for the last many years. It is a kind of software that helps designers, architects, and engineers to create a design. It is effortless to use, and user-friendly. With the help of AUTOCAD, one can draft the 2D design with high accuracy, which is difficult to achieve on drawing sheet.

As mentioned, AutoCAD has numerous capabilities that can be applied to an array of projects in various fields. Various kinds of designers are most likely to use the program and it is more common in design-centered fields, like architecture and engineering. However, many other professions, such as fine artists and mathematicians, may use the program to create visuals for their work. [33]

3.4.2 ProtaStructure

ProtaStructure is an innovative structural BIM solution for structural engineers to model, analyze and design buildings quickly and accurately. From one central model easily compare different schemes and automate steel and concrete design, reducing design time and increasing project profitability. It uses advanced integrated features including grouped member design, 3D FE Analysis, staged construction and seismic design, foundations and punching shear checks to quickly produce results. Handles changes with ease and seamlessly coordinate projects with architects, owners and other stakeholders with intelligent BIM integration. Produces high quality drawings and all design documentation from ProtaStructure automatically using included ProtaDetails and ProtaSteel. Saves time and increase project profits. [30]

3.5 MEMBERS DESIGN

Design of Slab, Beam, Column, Footing and Staircase with geometric parameters stated below:

1. Beam = 230×450mm, 230×600mm
2. Column = 230×300mm, 230×600mm
3. Slab = 175mm, 200mm

The software expressively used to carry out the design of the structural member was ProtaStructure.

3.6 DESIGN PROCEDURE OBJECTIVES

- i. Test for safe bearing capacity of soil.
- ii. Generating structural framing plan
- iii. Creating model in ProtaStructure
- iv. Application of loads on the member
- v. Analysis of the structure
- vi. Design the structure (software design).
- vii. Drawing & Preparation of Schedules
- viii. Detailing

CHAPTER FOUR

ANALYSIS, DESIGN & DISCUSSION

4.0 INTRODUCTION

This chapter contains the presentation of the architectural plans, the structural layout, the structural model, the analysis of the structure, and the design of the structure. As has been discussed in the previous chapter, the structural analysis and design were carried based on BS code requirements. Protastructure and AutoCAD were used to perform the architectural and structural design.

4.1 ARCHITECTURAL PLANS

The architectural plan drawings produced the imaginative and conceptual picture of the primary aim of this work. It gives a pictorial overview on which the structural analysis and design was founded. The scope was tuned to give an outstanding, unique and global taste matching the dynamic vision of the university which serves as the proposed client for this project. The conceptual plan covers a wide range of recreational activity in an enclosed complex. Nonetheless, it is limited to the basic scope of recreation. The plan was positioned to provide capacity for about 1000 users at once and to make accessible the following basic facilities:

- | | |
|-----------------------|-------------------------|
| i. Multipurpose Court | vi. Restaurant |
| ii. Mini Mart | vii. Suya Spot |
| iii. Electric room | viii. Cyber Centre |
| iv. Art room | ix. Store room |
| v. Spa room | x. Gymnasium hall |
| xi. Officials' room | xiii. Relaxation Joint |
| xii. Game room | xiv. Locker/Recess room |

- xv. Reception spot
- xvi. Cinema hall
- xvii. Stair hall
- xviii. Restroom
- xix. Entrances
- xx. Sports seats
- xxi. Cinema Hall seats

The grand plan was rationed to the dimension of 57.4m length by 40.2m breadth while the multipurpose court was planned to be 26.2m length by 15.0m breadth. The multipurpose court is to make provision for activity such as: Long tennis, Table tennis, Basketball and Volleyball.

Fig 4.0 Architectural drawing showing the proposed ground floor plan

Fig 4.1 Architectural drawing showing the proposed first floor plan

Fig 4.2 Architectural drawing showing the proposed first floor plan

4.2 STRUCTURAL LAYOUT

Technically, the structural layout can be preferred to as, a type of Engineering drawing, a plan or sets of plans for how a building or other structure will be built. Basic Structural Layout plans reveals the foundation, floor and roof plans. The structural drawings communicate the design of the building's structure to the building authority. It is drafted in a form that a builder can use for construction for easy establishment. It is an arrangement, plan or design of how a structure would be built. Structural layout provides information like size and location of the structural elements present in the respective plans. It is commonly known as General Arrangements (G.A).

In this project, the general arrangement was performed as frame building form, showing the columns, foundation base, beams and slabs. These arrangements were carried out to offer and satisfy the criteria for strength, serviceability, economy and safety.

Fig 4.3 Structural drawing showing the proposed first floor layout

Fig 4.4 Structural drawing showing the proposed Ground floor layout

Fig 4.5 Structural drawing showing the Suspended floor layout

Fig 4.6 Structural drawing showing the Roof layout

4.2 STRUCTURAL MODEL

The structural model for this project gave a visual representation in 3-dimensional view. The model was generated with the aid of the Protastructure software. The model shows the structural frame work, including the roofing system.

Fig 4.7 Structural drawing showing the structural model

4.3 ANALYSIS OF STRUCTURE

Structural analysis simply put involves the determination of the effects of loads on physical structures and their components. Structures subject to this type of analysis include all that must withstand load ranging from buildings, bridges, aircraft to ships. Structural analysis employs the fields of applied mechanics, materials science and applied mathematics to compute a structure’s deformations, internal forces, stresses, support reactions, accelerations and stability. The results of the analysis are used to verify a structures’s fitness for use, often precluding physical tests. This process is thus the key part of this project. The analysis was carried out to determine the bending moments, shear forces and deflections (displacements) caused by designed load for the different structure elements such as slabs, beams, columns and foundations. The analysis is preceded with the determination of the axial loads calculations carried out in the building analysis.

4.3.1 Axial Load Comparison Report

ANALYSIS AND DESIGN OF UNIVERSITY OF ABUJA INDOOR RECREATION MINI COMPLEX		Yenerbahce_ Istanbul_ (0001453)	
Axial Load Comparison Report PROJECT II JANUARY 2022 Rev: 1		Calc. By: ADEOYE O. VICTOR (16243005) Checked By:	

Axial Load Comparison Report

TOTAL LOADS (Based On Slabs Loads):

G - Dead Loads:

Storey	Column	Wall	Beam	Slab	Ribbed Slab	Total
3 (+9.90m)	681.6	0.0	5083.6	0.0	0.0	5765.3
2 (+6.60m)	855.4	0.0	1136.8	357.2	0.0	2349.4
1 (+3.30m)	1385.6	0.0	1397.48	17617.4	0.0	32977.8
Total						41092.4

Q - Live Loads:

Storey	Column	Wall	Beam	Slab	Ribbed Slab	Total
3 (+9.90m)	0.0	0.0	1198.3	0.0	0.0	1198.3
2 (+6.60m)	0.0	0.0	0.0	150.1	0.0	150.1
1 (+3.30m)	0.0	0.0	0.0	7343.6	0.0	7343.6
Total						8692.0

TOTAL LOADS (Decomposed to Beams):

G - Dead Loads:

Storey	Column	Wall	Beam	Slab	Ribbed Slab	Total
3 (+9.90m)	681.6	0.0	5083.5	0.0	0.0	5765.1
2 (+6.60m)	855.4	0.0	1494.0	0.0	0.0	2349.4
1 (+3.30m)	1385.6	0.0	31592.2	0.0	0.0	32977.8
Total						41092.3

Q - Live Loads:

Storey	Column	Wall	Beam	Slab	Ribbed Slab	Total
3 (+9.90m)	0.0	0.0	1198.3	0.0	0.0	1198.3
2 (+6.60m)	0.0	0.0	0.0	150.1	0.0	150.1
1 (+3.30m)	0.0	0.0	7343.6	0.0	0.0	7343.6
Total						8692.0

BUILDING ANALYSIS COLUMN AND WALL AXIAL LOADS:

Storey	G	Delta G	Q	Delta Q
3 (+9.90m)	5765.3	5765.3	1198.3	1198.3
2 (+6.60m)	7781.0	2015.7	1298.8	100.5
1 (+3.30m)	41092.5	33311.5	8692.0	7393.2
Total		41092.5		8692.0

4.4 DESIGN OF STRUCTURE

4.4.1 Slab Reinforcement Design

ANALYSIS AND DESIGN OF UNIVERSITY OF ABUJA INDOOR RECREATION MINI COMPLEX						Yenerkahce_ Istanbul_(0001453)	
Slab Reinforcement Design PROJECT II JANUARY 2022 Rev: 1						Calc. By: ADEOYE O. VICTOR(16249005) Checked By:	
Slab	d/h (mm)	q (kN/m ²)	L2 (mm)	M-sup (kN.m)	M-span (kN.m)	Req/Sup (mm ²)	S T E E L B A R S
			Support Mc = 4.5Support As = 323.14/452.39		SupTop: Y12-		
250(T1)							
1S15	6	11.900	4439.40	0.0829	0.0619	629.2/646.27	
175(B1)	144/175	5.000	6490.89	40.3	30.1		StrBot: Y12-
			Deflection Check: L/d = 30.83 < 33.74 *** Sufficient ***				
			Support Mc = 33.3Support As = 702.63/904.78		SupTop: Y12-		
125(T1)							
1S14	3	11.900	2230.00	0.0630	0.0630	296.8/452.39	
250(B1)	144/175	5.000	5109.64	7.7	7.7		StrBot: Y12-
			Deflection Check: L/d = 15.49 < 52.0 *** Sufficient ***				
			Support Mc = 12.2Support As = 296.80/452.39		SupTop: Y12-		
250(T1)							
1S79	4	11.900	5800.00	0.0450	0.0340	296.8/452.39	
250(B2)	132/175	5.000	3446.53	13.2	10.0		StrBot: Y12-
			Support Mc = 1.5Support As = 296.80/452.39		SupTop: Y12-		
250(T1)							
Slab Strip: X7 -- Storey: 1							

Materials: C20/25 / Grade 410 (Type 2)							
Slab	Type d/h (mm)	q (kN/m ²)	L1 L2 (mm)	C-sup M-sup (kN.m)	C-span M-span (kN.m)	As Req/Sup (mm ²)	S T E E L B A R S
			Support Mc = 0.6Support As = 296.80/452.39		SupTop: Y12-		
250(T1)							
1S18	6	11.900	1848.67	0.0649	0.0479	296.8/452.39	
250(B1)	144/175	5.000	2030.33	5.5	4.0		StrBot: Y12-
			Deflection Check: L/d = 12.84 < 52.0 *** Sufficient ***				
			Support Mc = 11.9Support As = 296.80/452.39		SupTop: Y12-		
250(T1)							
1S19	2	11.900	3000.60	0.0630	0.0630	296.8/452.39	
250(B1)	144/175	5.000	9692.58	14.0	14.0		StrBot: Y12-
			Deflection Check: L/d = 20.84 < 52.0 *** Sufficient ***				
			Support Mc = 13.0Support As = 296.80/452.39		SupTop: Y12-		
250(T1)							
1S20	2	11.900	2230.47	0.0860	0.0860	296.8/452.39	
250(B1)	144/175	5.000	7524.73	10.6	10.6		StrBot: Y12-
			Deflection Check: L/d = 15.49 < 52.0 *** Sufficient ***				

4.4.2 BEAM REINFORCEMENT DESIGN

ANALYSIS AND DESIGN OF UNIVERSITY OF ABUJA INDOOR RECREATION MINI COMPLEX
BEAM DESIGN RESULTS

Yenerbahce_ Istanbul_ (0001463)
Prota Structure 03.0 (04.2012) / Page: BD- 1

Axis: 1 Storey: 1

Etiyeller: C20/25 / Grade 410 (Type 2) (Links: Grade 410 (Type 2))

	1B1	L=9684.4mm	1B2	L=4430mm	1B3	L=2230mm
Beam H (mm)	230 x 600		230 x 600		230 x 600	
Flange Bf x Hf	---		---		---	
	C20/25 / Grade 410 (Type 2)		C20/25 / Grade 410 (Type 2)		C20/25 / Grade 410 (Type 2)	

Bending (Top Edge)...

M (kN.m)	330.1	580.9	444.3	245.6	20.4	24.1	89.3	134.1
d (mm)	539.0	539.0	539.0	557.0	539.0	539.0	557.0	539.0
K/K'	1.27	2.23	1.70	0.88	0.08	0.09	0.32	0.51
x (mm)	267.24	267.24	267.24	233.31	59.89	59.89	73.18	118.58
As (mm ²)	2152.69	3557.02	2784.31	1523.96	111.94	131.85	478.00	774.57
As' (mm ²)	407.12	1811.45	1038.74	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
As-min	234.05	276.00	234.05	234.05	234.05	234.05	234.05	234.05

Bending (Bottom Edge)...

M (kN.m)	40.0	420.4	4.3	17.0	47.6	57.4	38.9	
d (mm)	540.0	539.0	539.0	557.0	540.0	540.0	557.0	
K/K'	0.15	1.61	0.02	0.06	0.18	0.22	0.14	
x (mm)	60.00	267.24	59.89	61.89	60.00	60.00	61.89	
As (mm ²)	218.55	2649.19	23.53	90.13	260.43	314.08	206.29	
As' (mm ²)	0.00	903.62	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
As-min	276.00	234.05	276.00	276.00	234.05	234.05	234.05	234.05

Shear and Bending Design...

Vd (kN)	279.0	360.1	223.2	78.7	67.9	125.9		
v (N/mm ²)	2.25	2.82	1.80	0.63	0.55	1.02		
vc (N/mm ²)	0.69	0.76	0.82	0.59	0.39	0.44	0.56	
v-max (N/mm ²)	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	
Vnom (kN)		284.5		185.3		166.1		
Td (kN.m)		0.1		0.0		0.0		
vt (N/mm ²)		0.00		0.00		0.00		
vt-min (N/mm ²)		0.00		0.00		0.00		
b-sup (mm)	0.0	2500.0	1050.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Links	Y10-175	Y10-175	Y10-125	Y10-175	Y10-300	Y10-300	Y10-300	Y10-300

Deflection Check ...

L/d	18.34 < 25.57 OK			7.95 < 65.94 OK		4.0 < 59.05 OK		
-----	------------------	--	--	-----------------	--	----------------	--	--

Supplied Steel Areas (mm²)

Top Edge	2211.68	1206.37	3820.18	3820.18	X 1407.43	1005.31	1005.31	603.19	1206.37
Bot Edge	1608.49	3015.93	2412.74	1206.37	402.12	402.12	402.12	402.12	402.12

Steel Bars ...

Top.Sup.	6Y16	10Y16	10Y16		3Y16	3Y16	3Y16	
Top.Sup.	5Y16	9Y16	9Y16		2Y16	2Y16	3Y16	
Bot.Bars		8Y16		2Y16		2Y16		
Bot.Bars		7Y16						
Bot.Sup.		4Y16	4Y16					
Side Bar								

Project GA_REVISD

4.4.3 COLUMN REINFORCEMENT DESIGN

ANALYSIS AND DESIGN OF UNIVERSITY OF ABUJA INDOOR RECREATION MINI COMPLEX	Yenerbahce_ Istanbul_ (0001453)
Column Reinforcement Design PROJECT II JANUARY 2022 Rev: 1	Calc. By: ADEOYE O. VICTOR (16243005) Checked By:

Column Reinforcement Design

1C1 (1-5) (230x600)
(C20/25 / Grade 410 (Type 2))

No	N _{Top/Bot} (kN)	M _{11 Top/Bot} (kN.m)	M _{22 Top/Bot} (kN.m)
1	1116.1, 1131.4	-57.4, 28.6	-75.3, 36.5
2	1037.3, 1052.6	-57.3, 27.9	-81.6, 39.8
3	758.7, 774.0	-18.4, 10.4	-35.8, 17.2
4	982.4, 945.5	-46.9, 23.4	-65.9, 33.9
5	985.9, 949.0	-46.9, 23.5	-59.6, 27.0
6	989.1, 952.2	-49.1, 33.9	-62.6, 30.2
7	929.2, 942.3	-44.7, 13.0	-62.9, 30.7

Critical Loading: 2 · (G+Q · Ψ)

	min	Design
N	1052.6	1052.6 kN
M ₁₁	-57.3	0.0 kN.m
M ₂₂	-81.6	-93.8 kN.m
N _{max}	5002.6	

Concrete Cover = 25.0 mm

BS8110-
Cl.3.8.4.5

$$N_k h / F_{cu} = 0.305$$

$$\text{Beta} = 0.64$$

$V_{d(1e)}$ = 36.8 / 17.5 kN	Short Column...	A_s (Req):	%1.97	2722.55 mm ²
$\mu_{d(1e)}$ = 1.22 / 1.54 N/m ²	$L_{e1} / b_1 =$	A_s (Sup):	%2.13	2945.24 mm ²
$\mu_{(1e)}$ = 0.28 / 0.13 N/m ²	$L_{e2} / b_2 =$	6Y25		
Links = Y10-300	$M_{max(1e)} =$	0.0 / 0.0 kN.m		

4.4.4 PAD FOOTING DESIGN

ANALYSIS AND DESIGN OF UNIVERSITY OF ABUJA INDOOR RECREATION MINI COMPLEX	Yenerkahce_ Istanbul_ (0001453)
Pad Footing Design PROJECT II JANUARY 2022 Rev: 1	Calc. By: ADEOYE O. VICTOR.(16243005) Checked By:

Pad Footing Design

F1

Columns: FC1, FC3, FC4, FC5, FC6, FC39, FC40, FC41, FC42, FC43, FC44, FC45, FC46, FC47, FC48, FC49, FC50, FC51, FC52, FC53 (230.0 / 600.0 mm)

Critical Loading: (FC1 1: G*F) N = -1131.4 kN
M_x × M_y = 36.5 × 28.6 kN.m

Footing Dimensions: L_x × L_y = 2500.0 × 2500.0 mm
h = 1200 mm

Soil Stresses: $\sigma_{max} = 247.789 \leq 252 \text{ kN/m}^2$ (1.4×180 kN/m²) ✓

$\sigma_{min} = 197.765 \geq 0 \text{ kN/m}^2$ ✓

q₃=219.749 kN/m² q₄=247.789 kN/m²

q₁=197.765 kN/m²

q₂=225.805 kN/m²

Design

X Dir:

Bending: M = 154.7 kN.m/m
A_s(Req) = 2400.00 mm²/m
Shear Check (BS8110-Cl.3.4.5.2)
(At Column Face)
(At 'l' from Column)
Punching (BS8110-Cl.3.7.6.4)
(At Column Face)
(At '1.5d' from Column)

K_k' = 0.03 ≤ 1.0 ✓
A_s(Sup) = 2680.83 mm²/m **Y16-75**

v = 0.24 N/mm² ≤ v_{max} = 4.00 N/mm² ✓
v = 0.00 N/mm² ≤ v_c = 0.30 N/mm² ✓

V_t = 1361.6 kN V_{-eff} = 1383.5 kN
v = 0.73 N/mm² ≤ v_{max} = 4.00 N/mm² ✓
V_t = 0.0 kN V_{-eff} = 0.0 kN
v = 0.00 N/mm² ≤ v_c = 0.30 N/mm² ✓
K_k' = 0.02 ≤ 1.0 ✓
A_s(Sup) = 2680.83 mm²/m **Y16-75**

v = 0.21 N/mm² ≤ v_{max} = 4.00 N/mm² ✓
v = 0.00 N/mm² ≤ v_c = 0.30 N/mm² ✓

V_t = 1361.6 kN V_{-eff} = 1383.5 kN
v = 0.73 N/mm² ≤ v_{max} = 4.00 N/mm² ✓
V_t = 0.0 kN V_{-eff} = 0.0 kN
v = 0.00 N/mm² ≤ v_c = 0.30 N/mm² ✓

Y Dir:

Bending: M = 110.1 kN.m/m
A_s(Req) = 2400.00 mm²/m
Shear Check (BS8110-Cl.3.4.5.2)
(At Column Face)
(At 'l' from Column)
Punching (BS8110-Cl.3.7.6.4)
(At Column Face)
(At '1.5d' from Column)

4.5 DISCUSSION

In this project, the protastructure software was generally used to perform the analysis of the structural elements. Using this software, the structural analysis approach was shouldered by the numerical approximation technique popularly known as the **FINITE ELEMENT METHOD**.

The Finite element method approximates a structure as an assembly of elements or components with various forms of connection between them and each element of which has an associated stiffness. Thus, a continuous system such as plate or shell is modeled as a discrete system with a finite number of elements interconnected at finite number of nodes and the overall stiffness is the result of the addition of the stiffness of the various elements. The behavior of individual elements is characterized by the element's stiffness or flexibility relation. The assemblage of the various stiffness's into a master stiffness matrix that represents the entire structure leads to the system' stiffness or flexibility relation. To establish the stiffness or flexibility of a particular element, we can use the mechanics of materials approach for simple one-dimensional bar elements, and the elasticity approach for more complex two- and three-dimensional elements. The analytical and computational development are best effected throughout by means of matrix algebra, solving partial differential equations.

Early applications of matrix methods were applied to articulated frameworks with truss, beam and column elements; later and more advanced matrix methods, referred to as finite element analysis, model an entire structure with one-two-and three-dimensional elements and can be used for articulated systems together with continuous systems such as a pressure vessel, plates, shells, and three-dimensional solids. Protastructure software typically uses matrix finite-element analysis, which can be further classified into two main approaches: the displacement or stiffness method and the force or flexibility method. The stiffness method is the most popular by far thanks to its ease of implementation as well as

of formulation for advanced applications. The finite-element technology is now sophisticated enough to handle just about any system as long as sufficient computing power is available. Its applicability includes, but is not limited to, linear and non-linear analysis, solid and fluid interactions, materials that are isotropic, orthotropic, or anisotropic, and external effects that are static, dynamic, and environmental factors. This, however, does not imply that the computed solution will automatically be reliable because much depends on the model and the reliability of the data input.

The design process of structural planning and design requires not only imagination and conceptual thinking but sound knowledge of science of structural engineering besides the knowledge of practical aspects. The purpose of standards is to ensure and enhance the safety, keeping careful balance between economy and safety.

CHAPTER FIVE

SUMMARY, CONCLUSION & RECOMMENDATION

5.0 SUMMARY

The purpose of this study is to design a befitting, esthetical, pleasing and portable edifice, which will serve the community of university of Abuja for the increasing need of social development for both students and staffs.

Thus, the study explored the presentation of the conceptual design, structural layout, modelling, analysis using numerical method and structural design calculated using Protastructure software. In other to carry out a safe and economical design, the British Standard requirements were strictly considered throughout the course of the design. With the analysis and design carried out in this project, the desire to provide a befitting edifice that would serve as a recreation centre with fascinating architectural scope thus, placing the university community closer to actualising her global vision.

5.1 CONCLUSION

In this design work, we have addressed the increasing need for befitting indoor recreation centre, drafted the conceptual plan, translated the plans to structural layout, performed the analysis by finite element method, designed in accordance to British standard requirements, verified the design values and made necessary specifications to enhance the language of economy and safety in structural engineering. The aim of this project is to design a befitting, esthetical, pleasing and portable edifice, which will serve the community of university of Abuja for the increasing need of social development for both students and staffs.

Generally, by adopting the Soil Bearing capacity test carried out at the Faculty of Pharmaceutical sciences terrain and supplied by the works department of the

university. It was therefore assumed that at the depth of 1.2m, the foundation design for the proposed site would be based on the soil bearing capacity of 180KN/m². At the end of the design, bearing capacity of soil was found feasible for construction. The AutoCAD software was used for drafting the plans. The structure was analysed using ProtaStructure Software and was checked for safety. The structure was redesigned until the safety of the building is attained. The Design was carried out for structural elements (Slabs, Beams, Columns and pad footing). The designed indoor recreation complex proposed for the campus gives added value to the university. The mini-indoor complex will generate and enhance the university revenue, foster social development, promote cultural engagements and play a huge role in the overall development of the university.

5.2 RECOMMENDATION

Based on the results of this design work, it is essential to offer a set of engineering recommendations that would be applicable in the construction of the edifice. Considering the great role which recreation centre would play in the general development of the university.

The material selection was based on safety and economical satisfaction:

For Construction (Foundation – building height)

Storey height = 3300mm

c. Concrete:

- iv. Concrete mixing – 1:2:4
- v. Concrete grade – 25N/mm²
- vi. Constituent for all structural elements (footing, columns, slabs, beams)

d. Reinforcement Steel

- iv. Steel grade – 410N/mm²

- v. Classes of steel; Mild steel round bar, R and High Yield steel bar, Y
- vi. Constituent for all structural elements (footing, columns, slabs, beams)

For Roof structure (STEEL)

- xiv. Side lap Corrugated sheeting
- xv. 75mm x 50mm Steel Purlins @ 900mm c/c
- xvi. Long Span Aluminum Roofing Sheet
- xvii. 100mm x 50mm Steel Struts
- xviii. 150mm x 50mm Steel Kingpost
- xix. 150mm x 50mm Steel Rafter @ 1200mm c/c
- xx. 100mm x 50mm Steel Wallplate
- xxi. 150mm x 50mm Steel Tie-beam
- xxii. 100mm x 50mm Steel Bracing
- xxiii. 8mm Dia G.I Hook Bolt
- xxiv. G.I. Nut
- xxv. G.I. Flat Washer
- xxvi. Bitumen washer

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APPENDIX: DESIGN RESULT FOR DIFFERENT STRUCTURAL ELEMENTS

Axis: 1 Storey: 2

Etriyeler: C20/25 / Grade 410 (Type 2) (Links: Grade 410 (Type 2))

	2B1	L=9884.4mm	2B2	L=4430mm	2B3	L=2230mm
BxH (mm)	230 x 600		230 x 600		230 x 600	
Flange Bf:Hf	---		---		---	
	C20/25 / Grade 410 (Type 2)		C20/25 / Grade 410 (Type 2)		C20/25 / Grade 410 (Type 2)	

Bending (Top Edge)...

M (kN.m)	104.1	41.3	14.7	11.6	43.7	48.8	30.6	1.7
d (mm)	555.0	555.0	555.0	555.0	555.0	555.0	555.0	555.0
K/I ³	0.38	0.15	0.05	0.04	0.16	0.18	0.11	0.01
x (mm)	86.61	61.67	61.67	61.67	61.67	61.67	61.67	61.67
As (mm ²)	565.73	219.92	78.19	61.57	232.46	259.49	162.98	8.83
As' (mm ²)	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
As-min	234.05	234.05	234.05	234.05	234.05	234.05	234.05	234.05

Bending (Bottom Edge)...

M (kN.m)		7.9	3.2	61.6	41.4		7.3	12.2
d (mm)		555.0	540.0	540.0	555.0		555.0	540.0
K/I ³		0.03	0.01	0.24	0.15		0.03	0.05
x (mm)		61.67	60.00	60.00	61.67		61.67	60.00
As (mm ²)		42.25	17.72	336.72	220.42		39.01	66.44
As' (mm ²)		0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00		0.00	0.00
As-min		234.05	234.05	234.05	234.05		234.05	234.05

Shear and Bending Design...

Vd (kN)	31.5		15.4	21.8		34.3		31.9
v (N/mm ²)	0.25		0.12	0.17		0.27		0.25
vc (N/mm ²)	0.44	0.44	0.44	0.44	0.44	0.44	0.44	0.44
v-max (N/mm ²)	4.00		4.00	4.00		4.00		4.00
Vnom (kN)		172.6			172.6			172.6
Td (kN.m)		0.0			0.0			0.0
vt (N/mm ²)		0.00			0.00			0.00
vt-min (N/mm ²)		0.00			0.00			0.00
b-sup (mm)	0.0		0.0	0.0		0.0		0.0
Links	Y10-300							

Deflection Check...

L/d	17.81 < 59.33 OK			7.98 < 59.33 OK			4.02 < 59.33 OK		
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Supplied Steel Areas (mm²)

Top Edge	628.32	628.32	628.32	628.32	628.32	628.32	628.32	628.32	628.32
Bot Edge	628.32	628.32	628.32	628.32	628.32	628.32	628.32	628.32	628.32

Steel Bars...

Top.Sup.	2Y20		2Y20		2Y20		2Y20	
Top.Sup.								
Bot. Bars	2Y20		2Y20		2Y20		2Y20	
Bot. Bars								
Bot. Sup.								
Side Bar								

ANALYSIS AND DESIGN OF UNIVERSITY OF ABUJA INDOOR RECREATION MINI COMPLEX	Yenerbaw_e_ Istank4_ (0001453)
Column Reinforcement Design PROJECT II JANUARY 2022 Rev: 1	Calc. By: ADEOYE O. VICTOR (16243005) Checked By:

Concrete Cover = 25.0 mm
BS8110-
Cl.3.8.4.5
N_{min}F_{cu} = 0.086
Beta = 0.90

V ₍₁₂₎ = 0.1 / 1.4 kN v ₍₁₂₎ = 0.91 / 0.95 N/mm ² v ₍₁₂₎ = 0.00 / 0.03 N/mm ²	Short Column... L ₁ /b ₁ = 9.6 < 15.0 ✓ L ₂ /b ₂ = 10.8 < 15.0 ✓ M _{max(12)} = 0.0 / 0.0 kN.m	As (Req): %0.40 min 211.60 mm ² As (Sup): %2.38 1256.64 mm ² 4Y20
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2C73 (48-22) (230/230)
(C20/25 / Grade 410 (Type 2))

No	N _{Top/Bot} (kN)	M _{11 Top/Bot} (kN.m)	M _{22 Top/Bot} (kN.m)
1	33.9, 39.7	-4.4, 4.1	-0.1, -0.4
2	33.0, 38.8	-4.0, 3.8	-0.2, -0.2
3	21.0, 26.9	-4.0, 3.7	-0.3, 0.0
4	26.8, 31.8	-3.3, 3.1	-0.7, 0.3
5	29.6, 34.6	-4.2, 3.9	0.6, -0.9
6	28.1, 33.1	-4.1, 3.8	-0.6, 0.2
7	28.3, 33.3	-3.5, 3.2	0.5, -0.8

Critical Loading: 1 - (G+F)

	min	Design
N	39.7	39.7 kN
M ₁₁	-4.4	-4.9 kN.m
M ₂₂	-0.4	0.0 kN.m
N _{max}	4151.6	

Concrete Cover = 25.0 mm
BS8110-
Cl.3.8.4.5
N_{min}F_{cu} = 0.030
Beta = 0.96

V ₍₁₂₎ = 0.0 / 2.3 kN v ₍₁₂₎ = 0.88 / 0.90 N/mm ² v ₍₁₂₎ = 0.00 / 0.05 N/mm ²	Short Column... L ₁ /b ₁ = 9.1 < 15.0 ✓ L ₂ /b ₂ = 10.1 < 15.0 ✓ M _{max(12)} = 0.0 / 0.0 kN.m	As (Req): %0.40 min 211.60 mm ² As (Sup): %2.38 1256.64 mm ² 4Y20
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1C74 (49-22) (230/230)
(C20/25 / Grade 410 (Type 2))

No	N _{Top/Bot} (kN)	M _{11 Top/Bot} (kN.m)	M _{22 Top/Bot} (kN.m)
1	108.3, 114.1	-3.0, 1.9	-1.4, 0.7
2	106.7, 112.6	-2.3, 1.4	-1.3, 0.6
3	71.7, 77.6	-2.3, 1.5	-1.0, 0.5
4	90.9, 95.9	-1.5, 0.6	-2.1, 1.5
5	91.3, 96.4	-3.4, 2.5	-0.3, -0.3
6	94.0, 99.1	-3.1, 2.3	-1.8, 1.2
7	88.2, 93.3	-1.8, 0.8	-0.6, 0.0

Critical Loading: 1 - (G+F)

min Design

BEAM CAPACITY ANALYSIS REPORT

bw/h = Section Dimensions
 b'ht = Flange Dimensions
 Ac = Section Area
 As (t) = Support Top Edge Tension Steel Area (r: Required, s: Supplied)
 As (b) = Support Bottom Edge Tension Steel Area (r: Required, s: Supplied)
 As-s (t)/Ac = Support Top Edge Supplied Steel Percentage
 Md-ij(t) = Max. Support Moment (top edge in tension)
 Md-ij(b) = Support moment (tension at bottom edge, same combination)
 Mr-ij(t) = Moment Capacity at Support (top edge in tension)
 Mr-ij(b) = Moment Capacity at Support (bottom edge in tension)
 Vd-ij = Shear Force Associated with the Combination with Max. Moment

(Beam Tension Edge: t=Top, b=Bottom)
 (Beam Support: t=LHS, r=RHS)

Beam	Storey	bw (mm)	h (mm)	b'f (mm)	h'f (mm)	Ac (mm ²)	Asr-t(t) (mm ²)	Asr-t(b) (mm ²)	Ass-t(t) (mm ²)	Ass-t(b) (mm ²)	Ass-tAc (%)	Asr-t(t) (mm ²)
1B1	1	230.0	600.0	900.0	0.0	138000.00	2152.69	407.12	2211.68	1608.49	1.603	3526.34
1B2	1	230.0	600.0	520.0	0.0	138000.00	2784.31	1038.74	3820.18	1206.37	2.768	34.56
1B3	1	230.0	600.0	370.0	0.0	138000.00	159.22	314.08	1005.31	402.12	0.728	909.61
1B4	1	230.0	600.0	640.0	0.0	138000.00	1199.80	7.49	1206.37	8042.25	0.874	976.93
1B5	1	230.0	600.0	230.0	0.0	138000.00	655.46	0.00	1005.31	402.12	0.728	418.82
1B6	1	230.0	600.0	730.0	0.0	138000.00	2303.61	558.05	2412.74	8042.25	1.748	794.00
1B7	1	230.0	600.0	1310.0	175.0	138000.00	2974.58	1229.01	3015.93	1407.43	2.185	2852.38
1B8	1	230.0	600.0	810.0	175.0	138000.00	2554.01	808.44	3015.93	1005.31	2.185	212.31
1B9	1	230.0	600.0	510.0	175.0	138000.00	419.38	217.70	1005.31	402.12	0.728	1819.12
1B10	1	230.0	600.0	1050.0	175.0	138000.00	2040.42	294.85	2211.68	1005.31	1.603	428.86
1B13	1	230.0	600.0	1190.0	175.0	138000.00	2121.90	376.33	2211.68	1005.31	1.603	2334.27
1B14	1	230.0	600.0	810.0	175.0	138000.00	2129.03	383.46	2412.74	603.19	1.748	304.43
1B15	1	230.0	600.0	510.0	175.0	138000.00	428.31	69.65	1005.31	402.12	0.728	1495.30
1B16	1	230.0	600.0	1050.0	175.0	138000.00	1775.05	37.25	1809.56	8042.25	1.311	1640.81
1B17	1	230.0	600.0	500.0	0.0	138000.00	1366.87	0.00	1809.56	402.12	1.311	469.80
1B18	1	230.0	600.0	830.0	175.0	138000.00	562.46	148.10	603.19	804.25	0.437	636.35
1B19	1	230.0	600.0	540.0	175.0	138000.00	746.09	13.32	942.48	628.32	0.683	681.54
1B20	1	230.0	600.0	520.0	175.0	138000.00	687.85	12.19	942.48	628.32	0.683	296.40
1B21	1	230.0	600.0	370.0	175.0	138000.00	351.46	0.00	942.48	628.32	0.683	988.71
1B22	1	230.0	600.0	640.0	175.0	138000.00	1182.88	8.92	1570.80	942.48	1.138	1282.51
1B23	1	230.0	600.0	500.0	175.0	138000.00	1147.65	0.00	1570.80	628.32	1.138	202.66
1B232	1	230.0	600.0	370.0	175.0	138000.00	175.95	43.06	628.32	628.32	0.455	262.62
1B28	1	230.0	600.0	620.0	0.0	138000.00	1291.29	79.08	1570.80	942.48	1.138	1161.47
1B27	1	230.0	600.0	470.0	175.0	138000.00	929.25	0.00	1570.80	628.32	1.138	0.00
1B26	1	230.0	600.0	590.0	175.0	138000.00	510.65	22.14	628.32	628.32	0.455	358.10
1B25	1	230.0	600.0	300.0	0.0	138000.00	244.04	3.92	628.32	628.32	0.455	0.00
1B31	1	230.0	600.0	950.0	175.0	138000.00	1442.75	249.53	1608.49	8042.25	1.166	1941.01
1B30	1	230.0	600.0	450.0	175.0	138000.00	911.90	0.00	2010.62	402.12	1.457	354.71
1B29	1	230.0	600.0	750.0	175.0	138000.00	738.66	106.58	1005.31	804.25	0.728	756.41
1B34	1	230.0	600.0	950.0	175.0	138000.00	1111.04	238.18	1206.37	8042.25	0.874	1581.98
1B33	1	230.0	600.0	450.0	175.0	138000.00	727.72	0.00	1608.49	402.12	1.166	313.22
1B32	1	230.0	600.0	750.0	175.0	138000.00	643.75	104.90	1005.31	603.19	0.728	681.31
1B37	1	230.0	600.0	950.0	175.0	138000.00	1196.44	232.42	1570.80	942.48	1.138	1703.17
1B36	1	230.0	600.0	450.0	175.0	138000.00	798.87	0.00	1884.96	628.32	1.366	291.00
1B35	1	230.0	600.0	750.0	175.0	138000.00	612.35	111.44	628.32	628.32	0.455	664.78
1B40	1	230.0	600.0	950.0	175.0	138000.00	1434.36	248.14	1608.49	8042.25	1.166	1914.18
1B39	1	230.0	600.0	340.0	175.0	138000.00	855.28	0.00	2010.62	402.12	1.457	286.08
1B38	1	230.0	600.0	490.0	175.0	138000.00	441.89	70.94	603.19	402.12	0.437	470.25
1B47	1	230.0	600.0	950.0	175.0	138000.00	1267.41	232.18	1570.80	942.48	1.138	1759.41
1B46	1	230.0	600.0	340.0	0.0	138000.00	806.91	0.00	1884.96	628.32	1.366	249.10
1B45	1	230.0	600.0	490.0	0.0	138000.00	385.91	88.94	628.32	628.32	0.455	583.66
1B52	1	230.0	600.0	360.0	0.0	138000.00	38.07	45.24	628.32	628.32	0.455	85.07
1B51	1	230.0	600.0	470.0	175.0	138000.00	87.37	50.97	628.32	628.32	0.455	172.59
1B50	1	230.0	600.0	400.0	0.0	138000.00	170.00	35.52	628.32	628.32	0.455	167.79
1B49	1	230.0	600.0	470.0	175.0	138000.00	150.13	31.71	628.32	628.32	0.455	111.94
1B48	1	230.0	600.0	340.0	0.0	138000.00	90.46	2.65	628.32	628.32	0.455	66.46
1B53	1	230.0	600.0	730.0	175.0	138000.00	464.79	36.93	603.19	603.19	0.437	594.61
1B54	1	230.0	600.0	790.0	175.0	138000.00	494.95	90.93	1005.31	402.12	0.728	2219.70
1B55	1	230.0	600.0	430.0	175.0	138000.00	102.33	105.96	628.32	628.32	0.455	208.68
1B56	1	230.0	600.0	430.0	175.0	138000.00	103.68	86.76	942.48	628.32	0.683	1402.23
1B57	1	230.0	600.0	230.0	0.0	138000.00	198.38	159.79	628.32	628.32	0.455	703.34
1B58	1	230.0	600.0	280.0	0.0	138000.00	106.12	41.81	628.32	628.32	0.455	140.43
1B59	1	230.0	600.0	610.0	175.0	138000.00	306.73	66.90	628.32	628.32	0.455	233.85
1B60	1	230.0	600.0	470.0	175.0	138000.00	74.82	55.11	628.32	628.32	0.455	907.95
1B61	1	230.0	600.0	620.0	0.0	138000.00	1377.38	15.55	1570.80	942.48	1.138	1108.05
1B62	1	230.0	450.0	350.0	0.0	103500.00	22.96	70.28	628.32	628.32	0.607	41.80
1B63	1	230.0	450.0	340.0	0.0	103500.00	56.99	31.01	628.32	628.32	0.607	0.00
1B64	1	230.0	450.0	340.0	175.0	103500.00	50.60	34.81	628.32	628.32	0.607	0.08
1B65	1	230.0	450.0	340.0	175.0	103500.00	56.94	32.35	628.32	628.32	0.607	0.00
1B66	1	230.0	450.0	350.0	0.0	103500.00	23.62	70.24	628.32	628.32	0.607	41.36

BEAM REINFORCEMENT TABLE

Beam	Strý	Section	Top Bar	Top/LHS Sup.Bar	Top/RHS Sup.Bar	Top/LHS Sup.Bar	Top/RHS Sup.Bar
1B1	1	23/60	6Y16	6Y16	10Y16	5Y16	9Y16
1B2	1	23/60	7Y16	10Y16	3Y16	9Y16	2Y16
1B3	1	23/60	3Y16	3Y16	3Y16	2Y16	3Y16
1B4	1	23/60	2Y16	3Y16	3Y16	3Y16	2Y16
1B5	1	23/60	2Y16	3Y16	6Y16	2Y16	6Y16
1B6	1	23/60	2Y16	6Y16	3Y16	6Y16	2Y16
1B7	1	23/60	4Y16	8Y16	8Y16	7Y16	7Y16
1B8	1	23/60	6Y16	8Y16	3Y16	7Y16	2Y16
1B9	1	23/60	6Y16	3Y16	6Y16	2Y16	5Y16
1B10	1	23/60	2Y16	6Y16	3Y16	5Y16	
1B13	1	23/60	2Y16	6Y16	6Y16	5Y16	6Y16
1B14	1	23/60	4Y16	6Y16	3Y16	6Y16	2Y16
1B15	1	23/60	5Y16	3Y16	5Y16	2Y16	4Y16
1B16	1	23/60	2Y16	5Y16	5Y16	4Y16	4Y16
1B17	1	23/60	3Y16	5Y16	3Y16	4Y16	
1B18	1	23/60	2Y16	3Y16	3Y16		2Y16
1B19	1	23/60	2Y20	3Y20	3Y20		
1B20	1	23/60	2Y20	3Y20	3Y20		
1B21	1	23/60	3Y20	3Y20	3Y20		2Y20
1B22	1	23/60	2Y20	3Y20	3Y20	2Y20	2Y20
1B23	1	23/60	2Y20	3Y20	2Y20	2Y20	
1B232	1	23/60	2Y20	2Y20	2Y20		
1B28	1	23/60	2Y20	3Y20	3Y20	2Y20	2Y20
1B27	1	23/60	2Y20	3Y20	2Y20	2Y20	
1B26	1	23/60	2Y20	2Y20	2Y20		
1B25	1	23/60	2Y20	2Y20	2Y20		
1B31	1	23/60	2Y16	4Y16	5Y16	4Y16	5Y16
1B30	1	23/60	3Y16	5Y16	3Y16	5Y16	2Y16
1B29	1	23/60	2Y16	3Y16	3Y16	2Y16	2Y16
1B34	1	23/60	2Y16	3Y16	4Y16	3Y16	4Y16
1B33	1	23/60	3Y16	4Y16	3Y16	4Y16	2Y16
1B32	1	23/60	2Y16	3Y16	3Y16	2Y16	2Y16
1B37	1	23/60	2Y20	3Y20	3Y20	2Y20	3Y20
1B36	1	23/60	2Y20	3Y20	2Y20	3Y20	
1B35	1	23/60	2Y20	2Y20	3Y20		
1B40	1	23/60	2Y16	4Y16	5Y16	4Y16	5Y16
1B39	1	23/60	3Y16	5Y16	3Y16	5Y16	
1B38	1	23/60	2Y16	3Y16	3Y16		
1B47	1	23/60	2Y20	3Y20	3Y20	2Y20	3Y20
1B46	1	23/60	2Y20	3Y20	2Y20	3Y20	
1B45	1	23/60	2Y20	2Y20	2Y20		
1B52	1	23/60	2Y20	2Y20	2Y20		
1B51	1	23/60	2Y20	2Y20	2Y20		
1B50	1	23/60	2Y20	2Y20	2Y20		
1B49	1	23/60	2Y20	2Y20	2Y20		
1B48	1	23/60	2Y20	2Y20	2Y20		
1B53	1	23/60	2Y16	3Y16	3Y16		2Y16
1B54	1	23/60	5Y16	3Y16	6Y16	2Y16	6Y16
1B55	1	23/60	2Y20	2Y20	3Y20		
1B56	1	23/60	3Y20	3Y20	3Y20		2Y20
1B57	1	23/60	2Y20	2Y20	3Y20		
1B58	1	23/60	2Y20	2Y20	2Y20		
1B59	1	23/60	2Y20	2Y20	2Y20		
1B60	1	23/60	2Y20	2Y20	3Y20		2Y20
1B61	1	23/60	2Y20	3Y20	3Y20	2Y20	2Y20
1B62	1	23/45	2Y20	2Y20	2Y20		
1B63	1	23/45	2Y20	2Y20	2Y20		
1B64	1	23/45	2Y20	2Y20	2Y20		
1B65	1	23/45	2Y20	2Y20	2Y20		
1B66	1	23/45	2Y20	2Y20	2Y20		
1B67	1	23/45	2Y20	2Y20	2Y20		
1B72	1	23/60	2Y20	2Y20	3Y20		
1B71	1	23/60	2Y20	3Y20	3Y20		
1B70	1	23/60	2Y20	3Y20	3Y20		
1B69	1	23/60	2Y20	3Y20	3Y20		
1B68	1	23/60	2Y20	3Y20	2Y20		
1B73	1	23/60	2Y20	2Y20	2Y20		
1B74	1	23/60	2Y20	2Y20	2Y20		
1B75	1	23/60	2Y20	2Y20	3Y20		2Y20
1B76	1	23/60	2Y20	3Y20	3Y20	2Y20	3Y20
1B78	1	23/60	5Y16	8Y16	8Y16	8Y16	7Y16
1B77	1	23/60	7Y16	8Y16	3Y16	7Y16	2Y16
1B83	1	23/60	2Y20	2Y20	3Y20		
1B82	1	23/60	2Y20	3Y20	3Y20		2Y20
1B81	1	23/60	2Y20	3Y20	3Y20	2Y20	2Y20
1B80	1	23/60	2Y20	3Y20	3Y20	2Y20	

ANALYSIS AND DESIGN OF UNIVERSITY OF ABUJA INDOOR RECREATION MINI COMPLEX	Yenerbahce_ Istanbul_ (0001453)
Column Rebar List PROJECT II JANUARY 2022 Rev:1	Calc. By: ADEOYE O. VICTOR (16243005) Checked By:

Column Rebar List

Member	Storey	b ₁ (mm)	b ₂ (mm)	Longitudinal Steel	Lateral Steel
1C1	Storey: 1	230	600	4x1Y25 + 2x1Y25	Y 10-300
2C1	Storey: 2	230	600	4x1Y25 + 2x2Y25	Y 10-225
3C1	Storey: 3	230	600	4x1Y25 + 2x2Y25	Y 10-300
1C3	Storey: 1	230	600	4x1Y20 + 2x1Y20	Y 10-225
2C3	Storey: 2	230	600	4x1Y20 + 2x1Y20	Y 10-225
3C3	Storey: 3	230	600	4x1Y20 + 2x1Y20	Y 10-225
1C4	Storey: 1	230	600	4x1Y20 + 2x1Y20	Y 10-225
2C4	Storey: 2	230	600	4x1Y20 + 2x1Y20	Y 10-225
3C4	Storey: 3	230	600	4x1Y20 + 2x1Y20	Y 10-225
1C5	Storey: 1	230	600	4x1Y20 + 2x1Y20	Y 10-225
2C5	Storey: 2	230	600	4x1Y20 + 2x1Y20	Y 10-225
3C5	Storey: 3	230	600	4x1Y20 + 2x1Y20	Y 10-225
1C6	Storey: 1	230	600	4x1Y25 + 2x1Y25	Y 10-300
2C6	Storey: 2	230	600	4x1Y20 + 2x1Y20	Y 10-225
3C6	Storey: 3	230	600	4x1Y20 + 2x1Y20	Y 10-225
1C7	Storey: 1	230	600	4x1Y20 + 2x1Y20	Y 10-225
2C7	Storey: 2	230	600	4x1Y20 + 2x1Y20	Y 10-225
3C7	Storey: 3	230	600	4x1Y25 + 2x2Y25	Y 10-300
1C9	Storey: 1	230	600	4x1Y25 + 2x1Y25	Y 10-300
2C9	Storey: 2	230	600	4x1Y25 + 2x2Y25	Y 10-300
3C9	Storey: 3	230	600	4x1Y25 + 2x2Y25	Y 10-300
1C10	Storey: 1	230	600	4x1Y20 + 2x1Y20	Y 10-225
2C10	Storey: 2	230	600	4x1Y20 + 2x1Y20	Y 10-225
3C10	Storey: 3	230	600	4x1Y20 + 2x1Y20	Y 10-225
1C11	Storey: 1	230	600	4x1Y20 + 2x1Y20	Y 10-225
2C11	Storey: 2	230	600	4x1Y20 + 2x1Y20	Y 10-225
3C11	Storey: 3	230	600	4x1Y20 + 2x1Y20	Y 10-225
1C12	Storey: 1	230	600	4x1Y20 + 2x1Y20	Y 10-225
2C12	Storey: 2	230	600	4x1Y20 + 2x1Y20	Y 10-225
3C12	Storey: 3	230	600	4x1Y20 + 2x1Y20	Y 10-225
1C13	Storey: 1	230	600	4x1Y20 + 2x1Y20	Y 10-225
2C13	Storey: 2	230	600	4x1Y20 + 2x1Y20	Y 10-225
3C13	Storey: 3	230	600	4x1Y20 + 2x1Y20	Y 10-225
1C15	Storey: 1	230	600	4x1Y20 + 2x1Y20	Y 10-225
2C15	Storey: 2	230	600	4x1Y20 + 2x1Y20	Y 10-225
3C15	Storey: 3	230	600	4x1Y20 + 2x1Y20	Y 10-225
1C16	Storey: 1	230	600	4x1Y20 + 2x1Y20	Y 10-225
2C16	Storey: 2	230	600	4x1Y20 + 2x1Y20	Y 10-225
3C16	Storey: 3	230	600	4x1Y20 + 2x1Y20	Y 10-225
1C17	Storey: 1	230	600	4x1Y20 + 2x1Y20	Y 10-225
2C17	Storey: 2	230	600	4x1Y20 + 2x1Y20	Y 10-225
3C17	Storey: 3	230	600	4x1Y20 + 2x1Y20	Y 10-225
1C18	Storey: 1	230	600	4x1Y20 + 2x1Y20	Y 10-225
2C18	Storey: 2	230	600	4x1Y20 + 2x1Y20	Y 10-225
3C18	Storey: 3	230	600	4x1Y20 + 2x1Y20	Y 10-225
1C19	Storey: 1	230	600	4x1Y20 + 2x1Y20	Y 10-225
2C19	Storey: 2	230	600	4x1Y20 + 2x1Y20	Y 10-225
3C19	Storey: 3	230	600	4x1Y20 + 2x1Y20	Y 10-225
1C20	Storey: 1	230	600	4x1Y20 + 2x1Y20	Y 10-225
2C20	Storey: 2	230	600	4x1Y20 + 2x1Y20	Y 10-225
3C20	Storey: 3	230	600	4x1Y20 + 2x1Y20	Y 10-225
1C21	Storey: 1	230	600	4x1Y20 + 2x1Y20	Y 10-225
1C22	Storey: 1	230	600	4x1Y20 + 2x1Y20	Y 10-225
1C23	Storey: 1	230	600	4x1Y20 + 2x1Y20	Y 10-225
1C24	Storey: 1	230	600	4x1Y20 + 2x1Y20	Y 10-225
1C25	Storey: 1	230	600	4x1Y20 + 2x1Y20	Y 10-225
1C26	Storey: 1	230	600	4x1Y20 + 2x1Y20	Y 10-225
1C27	Storey: 1	230	600	4x1Y25 + 2x4Y25	Y 10-300
1C28	Storey: 1	230	600	4x1Y25 + 2x2Y25	Y 10-300
1C29	Storey: 1	230	600	4x1Y20 + 2x1Y20	Y 10-225
1C30	Storey: 1	230	600	4x1Y20 + 2x1Y20	Y 10-225